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Generalizations of Stirling Numbers and Normal Ordering

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“The goal of science is to make nature understandable, but the real motivation is often the search for mathematical beauty.”

— Paul Dirac

*To my parents,
for their unconditional love and silent sacrifices.*

*To my teachers,
for awakening in me the passion for knowledge.*

And to all those who supported me throughout this journey.

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Abstract

This thesis explores the interplay between fundamental concepts of quantum mechanics and certain combinatorial structures, particularly Stirling numbers. We begin by presenting the foundations of the quantum harmonic oscillator and introduce the concept of coherent states, highlighting their importance in the representation of quantum systems.

The second part of the work focuses on an in-depth study of Stirling numbers, from their classical combinatorial properties to their appearance in the normal and anti-normal ordering of quantum operators. Special attention is given to their generalization via q -deformation, providing insights into their role within deformed algebras and generalized quantum mechanics.

Finally, we construct and analyze Stirling operators for different quantum systems, in particular the hydrogen atom potential and the Pöschl-Teller potential. These operators help establish a link between combinatorial structures and physical observables, offering a novel perspective on the algebraic structure of quantum systems.

Keywords: quantum mechanics, harmonic oscillator, coherent states, Stirling numbers, q -deformation, Heisenberg algebra, quantum operators, potential systems.

Résumé

Ce mémoire explore l'interaction entre les concepts fondamentaux de la mécanique quantique et certaines structures combinatoires, notamment les nombres de Stirling. Dans un premier temps, nous présentons les fondements de l'oscillateur harmonique quantique et introduisons la notion d'états cohérents, en mettant en lumière leur rôle dans la représentation des systèmes quantiques.

La deuxième partie du mémoire est consacrée à une étude approfondie des nombres de Stirling, de leurs propriétés combinatoires classiques à leur émergence dans les relations d'ordre normal et anti-normal des opérateurs quantiques. Une attention particulière est portée à leur généralisation via la q -déformation, ce qui permet de mieux comprendre leur rôle dans le cadre des algèbres déformées et de la mécanique quantique généralisée.

Enfin, nous construisons et analysons des opérateurs de Stirling pour différents systèmes quantiques, en particulier pour le potentiel de l'atome d'hydrogène et celui de Pöschl-Teller. Ces opérateurs permettent de relier des structures combinatoires à des observables physiques et offrent ainsi un nouvel éclairage sur la structure algébrique des systèmes quantiques.

Mots-clés : mécanique quantique, oscillateur harmonique, états cohérents, nombres de Stirling, q -déformation, algèbre de Heisenberg, opérateurs quantiques, systèmes à potentiel.

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General Introduction

Since its emergence at the beginning of the 20th century, quantum mechanics has established itself as one of the fundamental pillars of modern physics, providing an essential theoretical framework for understanding microscopic phenomena. It is based on a particularly rigorous mathematical structure, involving tools from linear algebra, functional analysis, and group theory. As Dirac expressed it: “Mathematical physics must aim not only at truth but also at beauty.” [1], thus highlighting the aesthetic dimension inherent in the mathematical formulation of physical laws.

Among the most studied quantum systems, the harmonic oscillator occupies a central place. This model, both exactly solvable and conceptually fundamental, constitutes a basic foundation in many theoretical approaches. It also offers a privileged framework for the introduction of *coherent states*, situated at the boundary between classical and quantum regimes. These embody the idea formulated by Schrödinger: “The best quantum state is the one that most closely resembles a classical state.” [2].

Initially introduced by Schrödinger and formalized by Glauber in the 1960s in the context of quantum optics [3], coherent states allow a semi-classical representation of quantum states. They minimize the uncertainty product and exhibit remarkable algebraic properties related to the creation and annihilation operators. In particular, the normal ordering expansions of the powers of the number operator $(a^\dagger a)^n$ involve weighted combinations of operators $(a^\dagger)^k a^k$ with coefficients given by the Stirling numbers of the second kind. These coefficients reflect the combinatorial structure underlying the moments in coherent or thermal states.

As central objects in combinatorics, the Stirling numbers — of the first kind for counting permutations by their cycles, and of the second kind for set partitions — appear significantly in theoretical physics, particularly in the normal and anti-normal orderings of operators. As Gian-Carlo Rota put it: “Every operator structure has a hidden combinatorics.” [4], thus emphasizing the depth of the connection between algebraic analysis and combinatorial structures.

This relationship opens the door to rich investigations, where combinatorial tools become genuine instruments for analyzing quantum operators. The extension of these ideas to deformed algebraic structures, particularly through the q -deformation of the Heisenberg algebra, allows the generalization of Stirling numbers to their q -analogues.

These q -analogues preserve certain essential properties of classical combinatorial objects while introducing a parametric dependence that reflects algebraic deformations relevant to the quantization of symmetries, notably in statistical physics and quantum group theory.

This thesis is structured as follows. Chapter 1 introduces the harmonic oscillator and coherent states, first presenting their classical and quantum foundations, followed by their algebraic and physical properties. Chapter 2 presents the combinatorial properties of Stirling numbers, their generating functions, and their connection to quantum mechanics via normal ordering. This chapter sets the stage for the q -deformed generalization, presented in the final part of the chapter. Finally, Chapter 3 is devoted to Stirling operators applied to various quantum systems, particularly the hydrogen atom and Pöschl–Teller potentials, offering a unified framework between combinatorial structures and quantum algebras.

Chapter 1

Harmonic Oscillator and Coherent States

Introduction

The harmonic oscillator is a physical system corresponding to an object oscillating around an equilibrium position, such as a pendulum or a spring, which are two famous examples used to describe the behavior of a harmonic oscillator. The manipulation of these systems is simple: it involves a second-order differential equation that is easy to solve, all while remaining within a classical description.

One can also speak of the harmonic oscillator in quantum mechanics, for example when a charged particle is subject to a potential (or an atom in a crystal, an excited molecule, etc.). It oscillates around its equilibrium position, and this can be easily deduced using the fundamental principle of dynamics [5].

In this chapter, we will also discuss coherent states, which are particular solutions of the harmonic oscillator with different properties, such as their quasi-classical behavior and the minimization of the Heisenberg uncertainty principle [6]. These states play a very important role in the generalization of Stirling numbers, which is the aim of this thesis.

The treatment of the harmonic oscillator in quantum mechanics introduces important operators used to describe this physical system. These operators act in a specific way on the Hilbert space and due to their non-commutativity, their manipulation depends on the position of each in a given product. This introduces the notion of normal ordering, which plays an essential role in the generalization of Stirling numbers [7], the goal of this thesis work.

This chapter will cover the necessary theoretical foundations on the harmonic oscillator and coherent states, by defining the Hamiltonian of the system as well as the creation and annihilation operators and their properties.

1.1 Basic Theory of the Quantum Harmonic Oscillator:

1.1.1 The Classical Harmonic Oscillator

In classical mechanics, a particle undergoing oscillatory motion around an equilibrium position corresponds to a classical harmonic oscillator. Let us consider the case of a spring with stiffness k oscillating around its equilibrium position x_m . By applying the fundamental principle of dynamics (FPD):

$$m \frac{d^2 \vec{x}}{dt^2} = \vec{F}_l, \quad (1.1)$$

with $\vec{F}_l = -k\vec{x}$, the restoring force derived from the expression of the potential $V(x)$:

$$V(x) = \frac{1}{2}kx^2, \quad (1.2)$$

which gives:

$$\frac{d^2 x}{dt^2} + \omega^2 x = 0, \quad (1.3)$$

with $\omega = \sqrt{\frac{k}{m}}$.

$$\ddot{x} + \omega^2 x = 0. \quad (1.4)$$

This is a second-order differential equation that is easy to solve, and its solution is given by:

$$x = x_m \cos(\omega t + \phi), \quad (1.5)$$

where x_m and ϕ are constants determined by the initial conditions. It is a sinusoidal oscillatory motion around the point $x = 0$ with amplitude x_m and angular frequency ω .

The total energy is given by $E = \frac{1}{2}mv^2 + \frac{1}{2}m\omega x^2$, and it is conserved.

1.1.2 The Quantum Harmonic Oscillator

In quantum mechanics, the concept of energy from classical mechanics is treated as an eigenvalue of the Hamiltonian operator associated with energy.

Let us consider a charged particle placed in an electric potential. By applying the correspondence principle to the Hamiltonian of our system, where X (position) and P

(momentum) are given in the position basis $\{|x\rangle\}$ by:

$$\begin{aligned}\langle x|X|\psi\rangle &= x\psi(x), \\ \langle x|P|\psi\rangle &= \frac{\hbar}{i}\frac{\partial\psi(x)}{\partial x},\end{aligned}\tag{1.6}$$

where $\psi(x) = \langle x|\psi\rangle$.

Let us now define the commutation relation between X and P :

$$[X, P] = i,\tag{1.7}$$

also:

$$[X, X] = [P, P] = 0,\tag{1.8}$$

thus, the time-independent Schrödinger equation is given by:

$$\left\{\frac{\hbar^2}{2m}\frac{d^2}{dx^2} + \frac{1}{2}m\omega^2x^2\right\}\psi(x) = E\psi(x).\tag{1.9}$$

The solution of this equation can be rigorously carried out using the algebraic method. This involves introducing the creation and annihilation operators, which play a crucial role in the case of the harmonic oscillator. These operators allow us to describe the quantum states of the system more conveniently and facilitate calculations related to time evolution.

1.1.3 Creation and Annihilation Operators

Hamiltonian and Eigenvalue Equation:

First, we perform the following change:

$$\hat{X} = \sqrt{\frac{m\omega}{\hbar}}X \quad \text{and} \quad \hat{P} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{m\omega\hbar}}P,\tag{1.10}$$

where the observables \hat{X} and \hat{P} are now dimensionless.

In this case, the Hamiltonian can be written as follows:

$$H = \frac{P^2}{2m} + \frac{1}{2}m\omega X^2 = \hbar\omega\hat{H},\tag{1.11}$$

where $\hat{H} = \frac{1}{2}(\hat{X}^2 + \hat{P}^2)$ which represents the dimensionless Hamiltonian. Thus, instead of working with the eigenvalue equation $H|\psi_\nu\rangle = E_\nu|\psi_\nu\rangle$, we seek the eigenvalues of the Hamiltonian that satisfies the eigenvalue equation $\hat{H}|\psi_\nu\rangle = \epsilon_\nu|\psi_\nu\rangle$, where $\epsilon_\nu = \frac{E_\nu}{\hbar\omega}$.

Let us define the following operators:

$$\begin{aligned} a &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (\hat{X} + i\hat{P}), \\ a^\dagger &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (\hat{X} - i\hat{P}), \end{aligned} \tag{1.12}$$

we see that a^\dagger is the Hermitian conjugate of a .

Using (1.12), we can deduce the expressions of the operators \hat{X} and \hat{P} in terms of a and a^\dagger :

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{X} &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (a^\dagger + a), \\ \hat{P} &= \frac{i}{\sqrt{2}} (a^\dagger - a). \end{aligned} \tag{1.13}$$

Using the relation linking \hat{X} and \hat{P} , (1.7), we can easily deduce the commutation relation between a and a^\dagger , indeed:

$$\begin{aligned} [a, a^\dagger] &= \frac{1}{2} [\hat{X} + i\hat{P}, \hat{X} - i\hat{P}] \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \left(-i [\hat{X}, \hat{P}] + i [\hat{P}, \hat{X}] \right) \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \left(-2i [\hat{X}, \hat{P}] \right) \\ &= -i [\hat{X}, \hat{P}] \\ &= 1. \end{aligned} \tag{1.14}$$

Using (1.14), we can rewrite the Hamiltonian in terms of the annihilation and creation operators:

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{H} &= \frac{1}{2} (\hat{X}^2 + \hat{P}^2) \\ &= \frac{1}{2} (aa^\dagger + a^\dagger a) \\ &= a^\dagger a + \frac{1}{2}. \end{aligned} \tag{1.15}$$

Now let us introduce the operator $N = a^\dagger a$, the Hamiltonian can be rewritten as:

$$\hat{H} = N + \frac{1}{2}. \tag{1.16}$$

The commutation relations of N with the operators a and a^\dagger can be easily deduced:

$$[N, a] = -a \quad \text{and} \quad [N, a^\dagger] = a^\dagger. \tag{1.17}$$

Spectra of the Operator N :

To discuss the spectrum of N , one must determine its eigenstates or eigenvectors. These satisfy the properties summarized in the following three lemmas: The eigenvalues ν of N are positive or zero.

Proof. Let $|\psi_\nu\rangle$ be an eigenvector of N with eigenvalue ν ($N|\psi_\nu\rangle = \nu|\psi_\nu\rangle$). We have:

$$\begin{aligned} |a|\psi_\nu\rangle|^2 &= \langle\psi_\nu|a^\dagger a|\psi_\nu\rangle \\ &= \langle\psi_\nu|N|\psi_\nu\rangle \\ &= \nu\langle\psi_\nu|\psi_\nu\rangle, \end{aligned} \tag{1.18}$$

but $|a|\psi_\nu\rangle|^2 \geq 0$ and $\langle\psi_\nu|\psi_\nu\rangle > 0$ which implies that $\nu \geq 0$. \square

For a non-zero eigenvector $|\psi_\nu\rangle$ of N , with eigenvalue ν :

- If $\nu = 0 \implies a|\psi_\nu\rangle = 0$.

- If $\nu > 0$, then $a|\psi_\nu\rangle$ is an eigenvector of N with eigenvalue $(\nu - 1)$.

Proof. The first point follows easily from Lemma 1 ($|a|\psi_\nu\rangle = \nu\langle\psi_\nu|\psi_\nu\rangle = 0$ if and only if $\nu = 0$). For the second point of the lemma, we use the first relation of 1.17:

$$[N, a]|\psi_\nu\rangle = -a|\psi_\nu\rangle, \tag{1.19}$$

which gives:

$$\begin{aligned} Na|\psi_\nu\rangle &= aN|\psi_\nu\rangle - a|\psi_\nu\rangle \\ &= (\nu - 1)a|\psi_\nu\rangle. \end{aligned} \tag{1.20}$$

\square

Let $|\psi_\nu\rangle$ be a non-zero eigenvector of N with eigenvalue ν , then $a^\dagger|\psi_\nu\rangle$ is always non-zero and also an eigenvector of N with eigenvalue $(\nu + 1)$.

Proof. Since $\langle\psi_\nu|\psi_\nu\rangle > 0$ and $\nu \geq 0$, then $a^\dagger|\psi_\nu\rangle$ is always non-zero. We use here the second relation of (1.17).

$$[N, a^\dagger]|\psi_\nu\rangle = a^\dagger|\psi_\nu\rangle, \tag{1.21}$$

which gives:

$$\begin{aligned} Na^\dagger|\psi_\nu\rangle &= a^\dagger N|\psi_\nu\rangle + a^\dagger|\psi_\nu\rangle \\ &= a^\dagger\nu|\psi_\nu\rangle + a^\dagger|\psi_\nu\rangle \\ &= (\nu + 1)a^\dagger|\psi_\nu\rangle. \end{aligned} \tag{1.22}$$

For the first point of the lemma, we have:

$$\begin{aligned}
|a^\dagger |\psi_\nu\rangle|^2 &= \langle \psi_\nu | a a^\dagger |\psi_\nu\rangle \\
&= \langle \psi_\nu | (N + 1) |\psi_\nu\rangle \\
&= (\nu + 1) \langle \psi_\nu | \psi_\nu\rangle.
\end{aligned} \tag{1.23}$$

□

Theorem 1. *The spectrum of the eigenvalues of N consists of non-negative integers.*

Proof. The idea of this proof is to suppose that these eigenvalues are not integers, i.e.:

$$0 < \nu < n + 1, \tag{1.24}$$

taking the vectors $a |\psi_\nu\rangle$, $a^2 |\psi_\nu\rangle$, ..., $a^n |\psi_\nu\rangle$. Let us find the eigenvalues of these eigenvectors using the two relations from (1.17):

$$\begin{aligned}
[N, a^2] &= a [N, a] + [N, a] a \\
&= -a^2 - a^2 \\
&= -2a^2,
\end{aligned} \tag{1.25}$$

acting this on $|\psi_\nu\rangle$:

$$\begin{aligned}
[N, a^2] |\psi_\nu\rangle &= -2a^2 |\psi_\nu\rangle \\
\implies N a^2 |\psi_\nu\rangle &= a^2 N |\psi_\nu\rangle - 2a^2 |\psi_\nu\rangle \\
&= \nu a^2 |\psi_\nu\rangle - 2a^2 |\psi_\nu\rangle \\
&= (\nu - 2) a^2 |\psi_\nu\rangle,
\end{aligned} \tag{1.26}$$

we can easily conclude by induction that:

$$\begin{aligned}
[N, a^n] |\psi_\nu\rangle &= -n a^n |\psi_\nu\rangle \\
\implies N a^n |\psi_\nu\rangle &= a^n N |\psi_\nu\rangle - n a^n |\psi_\nu\rangle \\
&= \nu a^n |\psi_\nu\rangle - n a^n |\psi_\nu\rangle \\
&= (\nu - n) a^n |\psi_\nu\rangle.
\end{aligned} \tag{1.27}$$

We conclude that $(\nu - n)$ is the eigenvalue of N on the state $a^n |\psi_\nu\rangle$. Now consider the eigenvector $a (a^n |\psi_\nu\rangle)$ which has eigenvalue $(\nu - n - 1)$. According to (1.24), $(\nu - n - 1) < 0$, which contradicts Lemma 1 since $(\nu - n - 1)$ must be non-negative: $(\nu - n - 1) \geq 0$, which shows that $\nu = n$ is a non-negative integer. Thus, the eigenvalue equation of N becomes:

$$N |\psi_n\rangle = n |\psi_n\rangle, \tag{1.28}$$

□

So according to (1.11), the eigenvalues of the Hamiltonian are given by:

$$E_n = n + \frac{1}{2}. \quad (1.29)$$

The corresponding eigenstates are the same as those of N , namely $\{|n\rangle; n \geq 0\}$ which form an orthonormal basis.

Actions of a and a^\dagger on the state $|n\rangle$:

We show that:

$$a |n\rangle \propto |n-1\rangle, \quad (1.30)$$

so we can write:

$$a |n\rangle = \alpha_n |n-1\rangle. \quad (1.31)$$

Let us determine the value of α_n , we have:

$$|a |n\rangle|^2 = |\alpha_n|^2 |n-1\rangle|^2 = |\alpha_n|^2 \quad \text{since} \quad \langle n-1|n-1\rangle = 1, \quad (1.32)$$

also :

$$\begin{aligned} |a |n\rangle|^2 &= \langle n|a^\dagger a|n\rangle \\ &= n \langle n|n\rangle. \end{aligned} \quad (1.33)$$

Comparing (1.32) and (1.33), we get $\alpha_n = \sqrt{n}$. Hence:

$$a |n\rangle = \sqrt{n} |n-1\rangle. \quad (1.34)$$

The same reasoning allows us to prove that $a^\dagger |n\rangle \propto |n+1\rangle$. Writing $a^\dagger |n\rangle = \beta_n |n+1\rangle$, we obtain:

$$\beta_n = \sqrt{n+1}, \quad (1.35)$$

and also:

$$a^\dagger |n\rangle = \sqrt{n+1} |n+1\rangle. \quad (1.36)$$

Let us note the existence of a ground state $|0\rangle$ corresponding to the minimal energy $E_0 = \frac{1}{2}$, such that:

$$a |0\rangle = 0, \quad (1.37)$$

and that, from this state, all other excited states can be constructed by repeated

application of a^\dagger as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
a^\dagger |0\rangle &= \sqrt{1} |1\rangle \\
(a^\dagger)^2 |0\rangle &= \sqrt{1}\sqrt{2} |2\rangle \\
(a^\dagger)^3 |0\rangle &= \sqrt{1}\sqrt{2}\sqrt{3} |2\rangle \\
&\vdots \\
(a^\dagger)^n |0\rangle &= \sqrt{n!} |n\rangle,
\end{aligned} \tag{1.38}$$

and also by showing by recurrence that:

$$|n\rangle = \frac{(a^\dagger)^n}{\sqrt{n!}} |0\rangle. \tag{1.39}$$

We can also conclude that one can go from one eigenstate to the next using a^\dagger and conversely using the operator a , as illustrated in the following diagram:

Figure 1.1: Iteration of the creation operator a^\dagger on the state $|0\rangle$.

This is the reason why we call:

a^\dagger : creation operator.

a : annihilation operator.

N : number operator.

Ground state $\psi_0(x)$ of H :

To find the expression of the ground state, we use one of the properties of Lemma 1. $a|\psi_0\rangle = 0$ then:

$$\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \left(\sqrt{\frac{m\omega}{\hbar}} X + \frac{i}{\sqrt{m\omega\hbar}} P \right) |\psi_0\rangle = 0, \tag{1.40}$$

projecting (1.40) onto the basis $\langle X|$ and using (1.14) and (1.16), we obtain:

$$\begin{aligned}
\langle X| a |\psi_0\rangle &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \left(\frac{m\omega}{\hbar} x + \frac{d}{dx} \right) \psi_0(x) = 0, \\
\text{hence : } \frac{d\psi_0(x)}{\psi_0(x)} &= -\frac{m\omega}{\hbar} x dx, \\
\implies \psi_0(x) &= C \exp -\frac{m\omega}{\hbar} x^2,
\end{aligned} \tag{1.41}$$

with C the normalization constant:

$$\begin{aligned}\int |\psi_0(x)|^2 dx &= 1, \\ \int |C|^2 e^{-\frac{2m\omega}{\hbar}x^2} dx &= 1, \\ \implies C &= \frac{m\omega}{\pi\hbar},\end{aligned}\tag{1.42}$$

finally:

$$\psi_0(x) = \left(\frac{m\omega}{\pi\hbar}\right)^{\frac{1}{2}} e^{-\frac{m\omega}{\hbar}x^2}.\tag{1.43}$$

1.1.4 Wave function in phase space

Taking the time-independent Schrödinger equation already mentioned in the previous sections:

$$\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \frac{d^2\psi(x)}{dx^2} + \frac{1}{2}m\omega x^2\psi(x) = E\psi(x),\tag{1.44}$$

This is a second-order inhomogeneous differential equation to which we can apply separation of variables or the following change:

$$\epsilon = \frac{E}{\hbar\omega} \quad \text{and} \quad y = \left(\frac{m\omega}{\hbar}\right)^{\frac{1}{2}} x,\tag{1.45}$$

we then obtain a dimensionless differential equation:

$$\psi''(x) + (2\epsilon - y^2) \psi(x) = 0.\tag{1.46}$$

To find the solution of this differential equation, we first analyze its asymptotic behavior, that is, its extreme positions. In this case, we are interested in low energies, when the y^2 term dominates. In this form, the differential equation is approximately:

$$\psi''(x) = y^2\psi(x),\tag{1.47}$$

so the function ψ may be Gaussian, or something of similar form. Thus, we propose the following form of the wave function:

$$\psi(x) = u(y) \exp[-y^2/2],\tag{1.48}$$

by substituting this solution into the differential equation, we obtain:

$$u''(y) \exp[-y^2/2] - 2u'(y)y \exp[-y^2/2] + (2\epsilon - 1) u(y) \exp[-y^2/2] = 0,\tag{1.49}$$

simplifying the exponential term, we find:

$$u'' - 2yu' + (2\epsilon - 1)u = 0. \quad (1.50)$$

If we assume that the equation satisfied by $u(y)$ develops as a power series $u(y) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} C_n y^n$, we can make the substitution:

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} C_n [n(n-1)y^{n-2} - 2ny^n + (2\epsilon - 1)y^n] = 0, \quad (1.51)$$

analyzing the solution of the resulting series, we arrive at the recurrence relation:

$$C_{n+2} = C_n \frac{(2n+1-2\epsilon)}{(n+2)(n+1)}. \quad (1.52)$$

Let us examine what happens for large values of n . The recurrence relation becomes approximately:

$$\frac{C_{n+2}}{C_n} \sim \frac{2n+1-2\epsilon}{(n+2)(n+1)} \sim \frac{n}{(n+2)(n+1)} \sim \frac{1}{2}, \quad (1.53)$$

for fixed ϵ , but the coefficients C_n do not decrease fast enough for the series to converge, because even though the factor $e^{-y^2/2}$ has a Gaussian decay, the series in y^n may diverge (it grows faster than the exponential decays). This implies that the solution diverges at infinity, so it is not normalizable.

The only way to avoid this divergence is to require that the series ends after a certain number of terms. In other words, there must exist an integer n such that $C_{n+2} = 0$, which implies:

$$2n+1-2\epsilon = 0, \quad (1.54)$$

thus:

$$\epsilon = n + \frac{1}{2}. \quad (1.55)$$

This power series solution is not complete, since the individual eigenstates of the Hamiltonian are not yet orthogonal. Once this solution is established, we obtain a solution involving Hermite polynomials, in the form:

$$\psi_n(x) = \left(\frac{m\omega}{\pi\hbar}\right)^{\frac{1}{4}} \frac{1}{\sqrt{2^n n!}} H_n \left[\left(\frac{m\omega}{\hbar}\right)^{\frac{1}{2}} x \right] \exp\left(-\frac{m\omega}{2\hbar} x^2\right), \quad (1.56)$$

where $H_n = u(y)$ are the Hermite polynomials.

1.2 Introduction to Coherent States

Coherent states are special quantum states, often used to describe quantum systems that are close to classical behavior. In this chapter, we will discuss coherent states, their properties, why they are useful in quantum mechanics, and their relation to operators or Stirling numbers. The construction of this chapter will be based on the description [6].

1.2.1 Minimization of the Heisenberg Uncertainty Principle

The uncertainty principle in quantum mechanics states that it is impossible to simultaneously know the position and velocity of a quantum system. This is mathematically expressed by the following inequality:

$$\Delta x \Delta p \geq \frac{\hbar}{2}. \quad (1.57)$$

The states corresponding to minimal uncertainty are called coherent states. Coherent states $|z\rangle$ are eigenstates of the annihilation operator a :

$$a |z\rangle = z |z\rangle. \quad (1.58)$$

By expressing the position and momentum operators via a and a^\dagger , one can show that these states saturate the uncertainty inequality:

$$\Delta x \Delta p = \frac{\hbar}{2}, \quad (1.59)$$

thus, they are the most "classical" states in the quantum formalism, as quantum fluctuations are reduced to the minimum allowed.

This can be easily shown by taking the two definitions of x and p (1.13), then:

$$(\Delta x)^2 = \frac{\hbar}{2m\omega}, \quad (\Delta p)^2 = \frac{\hbar m\omega}{2} \implies \Delta x \Delta p = \frac{\hbar}{2}, \quad (1.60)$$

this proves that coherent states exactly minimize the product of uncertainties.

This minimization reflects the quasi-classical behavior of coherent states: although purely quantum, their dynamics in phase space resemble that of a classical point. This makes them fundamental tools in quantum optics, field theory, and semiclassical approaches.

1.2.2 Coherent States and Fock Space Representations

What is interesting in this part is that we can determine the states that may belong to the harmonic oscillator number states $|n\rangle$ treated in the first part. Let the completeness relation of number states be:

$$\mathbb{I} = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} |n\rangle \langle n|, \quad (1.61)$$

multiplying on the right-hand side of both sides of this equality:

$$|z\rangle = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} |n\rangle \langle n|z\rangle, \quad (1.62)$$

let us replace $\langle n|$ by the conjugate of equation (1.39):

$$\begin{aligned} |z\rangle &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} |n\rangle \langle 0| \frac{a^n}{\sqrt{n!}} |z\rangle, \\ &= \langle 0|z\rangle \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{z^n}{\sqrt{n!}} |n\rangle. \end{aligned} \quad (1.63)$$

Knowing that $a^n |z\rangle = z^n |z\rangle$. We can determine the coefficient $\langle 0|z\rangle$ by normalizing (1.63):

$$\begin{aligned} \langle z|z\rangle &= \langle 0|z\rangle \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{z^n}{\sqrt{n!}} \langle z|n\rangle \\ &= \langle 0|z\rangle \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{z^n (z^*)^n}{n!} \langle z|0\rangle \\ &= |\langle 0|z\rangle|^2 \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{|(z^n)|^2}{n!} \\ &= |\langle 0|z\rangle|^2 \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{z^{2n}}{n!} \\ &= |\langle 0|z\rangle|^2 e^{|z^2|}. \end{aligned} \quad (1.64)$$

Setting $\langle z|z\rangle = 1$, we get $|\langle 0|z\rangle|^2 = e^{-\frac{|z^2|}{2}}$. Hence:

$$|z\rangle = e^{-\frac{|z^2|}{2}} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{z^n}{\sqrt{n!}} |n\rangle. \quad (1.65)$$

Now taking (1.65) and replacing $|n\rangle$ by (1.39), we write $|z\rangle$ in terms of the ground state:

$$\begin{aligned} |z\rangle &= e^{-\frac{|z|^2}{2}} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{z^n}{\sqrt{n!}} \frac{(a^\dagger)^n}{\sqrt{n!}} |0\rangle, \\ &= e^{-\frac{|z|^2}{2}} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(za^\dagger)^n}{n!} |0\rangle, \end{aligned} \quad (1.66)$$

knowing that $e^x = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{x^n}{n!}$, (1.66) becomes:

$$|z\rangle = e^{-\frac{|z|^2}{2}} e^{za^\dagger} |0\rangle. \quad (1.67)$$

Finally, we note that we can determine any coherent state if we know the ground state of the harmonic oscillator.

1.2.3 Coherent State Wavefunctions

The annihilation operator a is defined according to [6] as:

$$a = \left(\frac{x}{2\Delta x} + \frac{ip}{2\Delta p} \right). \quad (1.68)$$

The eigenvalue z defining the coherent states (1.58) is defined as:

$$z = \left(\frac{x_0}{2\Delta x} + \frac{ip_0}{2\Delta p} \right), \quad (1.69)$$

where $x_0 = \langle x \rangle$ and $p_0 = \langle p \rangle$, the expectation values of the operators x and p respectively. Now let us find the expression of $\psi(x)$, the wavefunction of coherent states. Taking (1.68):

$$a = \frac{1}{2\Delta x} \left(x + i \frac{2p\Delta x}{2\Delta p} \right) = \frac{1}{2\Delta x} \left(x + i \frac{2p\Delta x^2}{\hbar} \right), \quad (1.70)$$

so:

$$a = \frac{1}{2\Delta x} \left(x + 2\Delta x^2 \frac{d}{dx} \right), \quad (1.71)$$

we used the fact that $\Delta x \Delta p = \frac{\hbar}{2}$ and $p = -i\hbar \frac{d}{dx}$. Using eq (1.58):

$$\frac{1}{2\Delta x} \left(x + 2\Delta x^2 \frac{d}{dx} \right) \psi = \left(\frac{x_0}{2\Delta x} + \frac{ip_0}{2\Delta p} \right) \psi, \quad (1.72)$$

which gives:

$$\frac{d\psi}{dx} = \frac{1}{2\Delta x^2} (x_0 - x) \psi + i \frac{p_0}{2\Delta x \Delta p} \psi \quad (1.73)$$

which finally gives the differential equation satisfied by ψ :

$$-i\hbar \frac{d\psi}{dx} = \left[\frac{i\hbar}{2\Delta x^2} (x - x_0) + p_0 \right] \psi, \quad (1.74)$$

from which we deduce the solution of (1.74) in the following form:

$$\psi(x) = \left(\frac{1}{2\pi\Delta x^2} \right)^{\frac{1}{4}} e^{-\frac{(x-x_0)^2}{4\Delta x^2} + i\frac{p_0(x-x_0)}{\hbar}}, \quad (1.75)$$

$\left(\frac{1}{2\pi\Delta x^2} \right)^{\frac{1}{4}}$ is deduced after normalization.

1.2.4 Completeness Relation

In quantum mechanics, the completeness relation is a fundamental property of orthonormal bases in a Hilbert space. It states that the basis vectors allow the complete representation of any vector in the space. This property is essential for quantum calculations, as it ensures that all information about the state of a system is accessible in this space.

Let $|z\rangle$ and $|z'\rangle$ be two different coherent states:

$$\begin{cases} |z\rangle = e^{-\frac{|z|^2}{2}} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{z^n}{\sqrt{n!}} |n\rangle, & (1) \\ |z'\rangle = e^{-\frac{|z'|^2}{2}} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{z'^n}{\sqrt{n!}} |n\rangle, & (2) \end{cases} \quad (1.76)$$

(1)[†] * (2) gives:

$$\begin{aligned} \langle z|z'\rangle &= e^{-\frac{|z|^2}{2}} e^{-\frac{|z'|^2}{2}} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{z'^n (z^*)^n}{n!} \\ &= e^{z'z^*} e^{-\frac{|z|^2}{2}} e^{-\frac{|z'|^2}{2}}, \end{aligned} \quad (1.77)$$

finally:

$$\langle z|z'\rangle = e^{-\frac{|z-z'|^2}{2}}. \quad (1.78)$$

The factor $e^{-|z-z'|^2}$ ensures that the integral of the sum of projectors $|z\rangle\langle z|$ gives the identity, i.e., there is no loss of information from the coherent states. This exponential behavior guarantees the proper normalization of the integral. Let us now verify the

completeness relation:

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{1}{\pi} \int dz^2 |z\rangle \langle z| &= \frac{1}{\pi} \int dz^2 \left(e^{-\frac{|z|^2}{2}} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{z^n}{\sqrt{n!}} |n\rangle \right) \left(e^{-\frac{|z|^2}{2}} \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \langle m| \frac{(z^*)^m}{\sqrt{m!}} \right) \\
&= \frac{1}{\pi} \int dz^2 e^{-|z|^2} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} |n\rangle \langle m| \frac{z^n (z^*)^m}{\sqrt{n!m!}} \\
&= \frac{1}{\pi} \sum_{n,m=0}^{\infty} \frac{|n\rangle \langle m|}{\sqrt{n!m!}} \int dz^2 e^{-|z|^2} z^n (z^*)^m,
\end{aligned} \tag{1.79}$$

Let $z = re^{i\theta}$ and compute the integral:

$$\begin{aligned}
I &= \int_0^{\infty} \int_0^{2\pi} e^{-r^2} r^{n+m} e^{i(n-m)\theta} r dr d\theta \\
&= \int_0^{\infty} \left(\int_0^{2\pi} e^{i(n-m)\theta} d\theta \right) e^{-r^2} r^{n+m+1} dr \\
&= 2\pi \int_0^{\infty} \delta_{nm} e^{-r^2} r^{n+m+1} dr,
\end{aligned} \tag{1.80}$$

for $n = m$, we obtain:

$$\begin{aligned}
I &= 2\pi \int_0^{\infty} e^{-r^2} r^{2n+1} dr \\
&= 2\pi \frac{n!}{2} = n!\pi,
\end{aligned} \tag{1.81}$$

which gives:

$$\frac{1}{\pi} \int dz^2 |z\rangle \langle z| = \frac{1}{\pi} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{|n\rangle \langle n|}{n!} \pi n! = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} |n\rangle \langle n| = \mathbb{I}, \tag{1.82}$$

which verifies the completeness relation.

Chapter 2

Overview of Stirling Numbers

Introduction

In 18th century Scotland, a young man named James Stirling lived. Passionate about the mysteries of mathematics, he lived in an era where science was experiencing a new boom, between Newton, Leibniz, and the beginnings of infinitesimal calculus. James Stirling, although rather discreet in major scientific circles, was nonetheless a sharp and perceptive mind. In 1730, in his work *Methodus Differentialis*, he explored approximation methods and was interested in sequences and series, unknowingly laying the foundation for a family of mathematical objects that would span centuries: the Stirling numbers [8].

But these numbers, as we know them today, did not appear all at once, as if by magic. They were named after Stirling, of course, but their combinatorial definition emerged later, thanks to the work of many mathematicians. These mysterious numbers, which are distinguished in two kinds — the first and the second — arise from simple questions: How many ways can we permute objects into cycles? Or how many ways can we partition a set? The first kind of Stirling numbers is indeed related to permutations and cycles, while the second kind counts set partitions [4].

Over time, the Stirling numbers of the first kind turned out to be linked to permutations and cycles, while those of the second kind allowed the counting of partitions of a finite set. Combinatorists of the 19th century, like Charles Hermite [9], deepened these objects by discovering their connection to generating series, polynomials, and matrices.

Then, in the 20th century, as mathematics became more and more abstract and interconnected, Stirling numbers ventured beyond simple combinatorics. They were found in operator theory, in asymptotic expansions, in analysis, in polynomial bases, in special functions, and even in quantum physics, via normal ordering problems, quantum oscillators, or bosonic statistics [3, 10]. Modern research has generalized these numbers

to q -deformed forms and linked them to advanced algebraic structures such as quantum groups [11].

Today, Stirling numbers are no longer merely combinatorial objects. They have become actors in a vast mathematical theater, appearing in algebra, geometry, topology, and even information theory. They have even been generalized: q -deformed, interpolated, non-integer, or related to abstract algebraic structures like quantum groups [4].

Thus, from Stirling's calculations in the 18th century to the equations of modern theoretical physics, the Stirling numbers have written their own story — a story of cycles, partitions... and mathematical beauty [1].

2.1 Combinatorial Origin

2.1.1 Set Partitions

Partitions play a central role in mathematics and especially in discrete mathematics and combinatorics. They allow us to model situations where a set of objects must be grouped into disjoint subsets, which arise in fundamental problems of classification, data structuring, and enumeration. In combinatorics, for example, one of the main goals is to determine how many ways a finite set can be partitioned into non-empty subsets. This question gives rise to combinatorial sequences such as the Stirling numbers of the second kind.

Let S be a set of natural numbers including 0, $S \subseteq \mathbb{N}_0$ with $\mathbb{N}_0 = \mathbb{N} \cup \{0\}$. π is called a partition set if there exists a collection of non-empty and disjoint subsets B_1, B_2, \dots, B_k of S in π such that: $\bigcup_{i=1}^k B_i = S$. The elements of π , which are the subsets B_1, B_2, \dots, B_k , are called blocks. The size (number of elements in B) of each block is defined as $|B|$ [12].

Example :

Consider the set $S = \{1, 2, 3\}$. The possible partition sets of this set are:

$$\{1, 2, 3\} ; \{1, 2\}, \{3\} ; \{1, 3\}, \{2\} ; \{2, 3\}, \{1\} ; \{1\}, \{2\} \text{ and } \{3\}.$$

2.1.2 Stirling Numbers of the First Kind

Stirling numbers of the first kind naturally arise in combinatorics through the study of permutations and their internal structures. More precisely, they allow counting the permutations of a finite set according to the number of disjoint cycles they contain. These numbers play an important role not only in combinatorial calculus, but also in analysis, algebra, and some branches of mathematical physics, particularly through series expansions and polynomial bases.

The Stirling numbers of the first kind, denoted $s(n, k)$, count the number of permutations of n elements that are composed of k disjoint cycles, that is, $s(n, k)$ is the number of ways to permute n elements such that the cycle decomposition contains exactly k cycles. The following table gives the Stirling numbers of the first kind for $1 \leq m, k \leq 5$:

$k \backslash n$	1	2	3	4	5
1	1	1	2	6	24
2		1	3	11	50
3			1	6	35
4				1	10
5					1

Table 2.1: *The Stirling numbers of the first kind (absolute values).*

2.1.3 Stirling Numbers of the Second Kind

Stirling numbers of the second kind play a central role in combinatorics, particularly in the study of partitions of finite sets. They help answer a fundamental question: in how many ways can a set of n elements be divided into exactly k non-empty, disjoint subsets? This idea is essential in clustering problems, classification, and modeling hierarchical structures.

Beyond their role in enumerative combinatorics, these numbers appear in various branches of mathematics, such as probability theory (e.g., in the calculation of moments), algebra (polynomial bases), and even in theoretical computer science (dynamic programming, data structures). They are also related to other well-known sequences, such as the Bell numbers, which count the total number of partitions of a set.

A partition of the set $[n] \equiv \{1, 2, 3, \dots, n\}$ is an equivalence relation on this set. The equivalence classes are called *parts*. $\left\{ \begin{smallmatrix} n \\ k \end{smallmatrix} \right\}$ denotes the number of ways to partition the set $[n]$ into k non-empty subsets, that is, the Stirling numbers of the second kind $S(n, k)$ (with a capital "S"), also known as *Stirling partition numbers*. They count the number of ways to partition a set of n elements into k non-empty subsets. In other words, it is the number of ways to place n distinct balls into k indistinguishable boxes such that no box is empty. By definition, $S(n, k) = 0$ if $k = 0$ or $k > n$, and $S(0, 0) = 1$. The following table (Table 1) gives the values of the Stirling numbers of the second kind, $\left\{ \begin{smallmatrix} n \\ k \end{smallmatrix} \right\} \equiv S(n, k)$ for $0 \leq k \leq n$ and $0 \leq n \leq 5$. [13]

For example, let $S = \{a, b, c\}$. There are 5 partitions of the set S , namely:

- $\{\{a, b, c\}\}$ (the set itself),

$k \backslash n$	1	2	3	4	5
1	1	1	1	1	1
2		1	3	7	15
3			1	6	25
4				1	10
5					1

Table 2.2: *The Stirling numbers of the second kind.*

- the partition consisting of three singletons: $\{\{a\}, \{b\}, \{c\}\}$,
- and the three partitions consisting of two subsets:

$$\{\{a\}, \{b, c\}\}; \quad \{\{b\}, \{a, c\}\}; \quad \{\{c\}, \{a, b\}\}. \quad (2.1)$$

2.1.4 Combinatorial Expression of the Stirling Numbers of the Second Kind

Let us write the number operator N in normal order as follows:

$$(a^\dagger a)^n = \sum_{k=1}^n S(n, k) (a^\dagger)^k a^k, \quad (2.2)$$

which uniquely defines the sequences of integers $S(n, k)$ for $k = 1, \dots, n$; these sequences are called the Stirling numbers. These numbers count the ways to partition n applications of $a^\dagger a$ into k pairs of $a^\dagger a$. The information about this sequence for each n can be represented by Bell polynomials :

$$B(n, x) = \sum_{k=1}^n S(n, k) x^k, \quad (2.3)$$

if we make the following substitution:

$$a^\dagger \leftrightarrow X, \quad a \leftrightarrow D, \quad (2.4)$$

where X is defined as multiplication by x , and $D = \frac{d}{dx}$ as the derivative. This substitution does not affect the commutator (1.14) because $[D, X] = 1$. Then (2.2) can be written as:

$$(XD)^n = \sum_{k=1}^n S(n, k) X^k D^k. \quad (2.5)$$

where the x^k counts the number of ways to partition k elements into k non-empty subsets. Now applying (2.5) to e^x , we compute:

$$(XD)^n e^x = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} S(n, k) X^k D^k e^x = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} S(n, k) x^k e^x = e^x \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} S(n, k) x^k, \quad (2.6)$$

where $D^k e^x = \frac{d^k}{dx^k} e^x = e^x$ and $X^k e^x = x^k e^x$. Similarly, we have:

$$(XD)^n e^x = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} (XD)^n \frac{x^k}{k!}, \quad (2.7)$$

knowing that:

$$(XD)^n x^k = x^n k^n x^{k-n} = k^n x^k, \quad (2.8)$$

we obtain:

$$(XD)^n e^x = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} k^n \frac{x^k}{k!}, \quad (2.9)$$

By comparing (2.6) and (2.9), we deduce the Debinski relation:

$$\sum_{k=0}^{\infty} k^n \frac{x^k}{k!} = e^x \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} S(n, k) x^k. \quad (2.10)$$

Using Debinski's relation, we can write the Bell polynomials (2.3) as:

$$B(n, x) = e^{-x} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} k^n \frac{x^k}{k!}. \quad (2.11)$$

Replacing $e^{-x} = \sum_{l=0}^{\infty} (-1)^l \frac{x^l}{l!}$, we find:

$$\begin{aligned} B(n, x) &= \sum_{l=0}^{\infty} (-1)^l \frac{x^l}{l!} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} k^n \frac{x^k}{k!} \\ &= \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} \binom{k}{j} (-1)^{k-j} j^n \frac{x^k}{k!}. \end{aligned} \quad (2.12)$$

By comparing (2.3) and (2.12), we conclude:

$$S(n, k) = \frac{1}{k!} \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} \binom{k}{j} (-1)^{k-j} j^n, \quad (2.13)$$

which gives the combinatorial definition of the Stirling numbers of the second kind.

2.1.5 Recurrence Relations

The Stirling numbers of the second kind $S(n, k)$ satisfy the following recurrence relation:

$$S(n, k) = S(n-1, k-1) + kS(n-1, k). \quad (2.14)$$

Proof:

We take the explicit formula for the Stirling numbers of the second kind (2.13), then:

$$\begin{aligned} S(n, k) &= \frac{1}{k!} \sum_{j=0}^{k-1} (-1)^{k-j} \binom{k}{j} j^n + \frac{1}{k!} (-1)^{k-k} \binom{k}{k} k^n \\ &= \frac{1}{k!} \sum_{j=0}^{k-1} (-1)^{k-j} \binom{k}{j} j^n + \frac{k^n}{k!}, \end{aligned} \quad (2.15)$$

where $\binom{k}{k} = 1$. Using the fact that $j \binom{k}{j} = k \binom{k-1}{j-1}$, equation (2.15) becomes:

$$S(n, k) = \frac{1}{k!} \sum_{j=0}^{k-1} (-1)^{k-j} k \binom{k-1}{j-1} j^{n-1} + \frac{k^n}{k!}, \quad (2.16)$$

We can verify that $k \binom{k-1}{j-1} = \left[\binom{k}{j} - \binom{k-1}{j} \right]$, then:

$$\begin{aligned} S(n, k) &= \frac{1}{k!} \sum_{j=0}^{k-1} (-1)^{k-j} k \left[\binom{k}{j} - \binom{k-1}{j} \right] j^{n-1} + \frac{k^n}{k!} \\ &= \frac{1}{(k-1)!} \sum_{j=0}^{k-1} (-1)^{k-j} \left[\binom{k}{j} - \binom{k-1}{j} \right] j^{n-1} + \frac{k^n}{k!} \\ &= \frac{1}{(k-1)!} \sum_{j=0}^{k-1} (-1)^{k-j-1} \binom{k-1}{j} j^{n-1} + \frac{k}{k!} \sum_{j=0}^{k-1} (-1)^{k-j} \binom{k}{j} j^{n-1} + \frac{k k^{n-1}}{k!} \\ &= \frac{1}{(k-1)!} \sum_{j=0}^{k-1} (-1)^{k-j-1} \binom{k-1}{j} j^{n-1} + \frac{k}{k!} \sum_{j=0}^k (-1)^{k-j} \binom{k}{j} j^{n-1}, \end{aligned} \quad (2.17)$$

from which we can easily conclude:

$$S(n+1, k) = S(n, k-1) + k S(n, k). \quad (2.18)$$

The Stirling numbers of the first kind satisfy the following recurrence formula:

$$s(k+1, n) = s(k, n-1) - k s(k, n). \quad (2.19)$$

2.1.6 Generating Functions

Ordinary Generating Function

In this section, we introduce the concept of the ordinary generating function for the Stirling numbers of the second kind [14]. These functions are very useful in our context to explicitly derive recurrence formulas. They also help us count numbers in a set, which connects with our concept of counting partitions into k blocks.

We base this section on the development made in [15].

Theorem 2. *The generating function for the Stirling numbers of the second kind is given by:*

$$\sum_{n \geq k} S(n, k)x^n = \frac{x^k}{(1-x)(1-2x)\dots(1-kx)}. \quad (2.20)$$

Proof:

Let:

$$\bar{H}_k(x) = \sum_{n \geq k} S(n, k)x^n, \quad (2.21)$$

Using the recurrence formula for Stirling numbers (2.18) shown earlier:

$$S(n, k) = S(n-1, k-1) + kS(n-1, k), \quad (2.22)$$

for $k = 1$, we have:

$$S(n, 1) = S(n-1, 1) + S(n-1, 0), \quad (2.23)$$

introducing the sum to make the generating function appear:

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} S_1(n, 1)x^n &= \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} S_1(n-1, 1)x^n + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} S_1(n-1, 0)x^n \\ &= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} S_1(n, 1)x^{n+1} + \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} S_1(n, 0)x^{n+1} \\ &= x \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} S_1(n, 1)x^n + x, \end{aligned} \quad (2.24)$$

then:

$$\bar{H}_1(x) = x\bar{H}_1(x) + x \implies (1-x)\bar{H}_1(x) = x, \quad (2.25)$$

thus we finally conclude that the generating function for $k = 1$ is:

$$\bar{H}_1(x) = \sum_{n \geq 1} S(n, 1)x^n = \frac{x}{1-x}. \quad (2.26)$$

Similarly for $k = 2$, we find:

$$\bar{H}_2(x) = \sum_{n \geq 2} S(n, 2)x^n = \frac{x^2}{(1-x)(1-2x)}. \quad (2.27)$$

By recurrence, we deduce:

$$\bar{H}_k(x) = \sum_{n \geq k} S(n, k)x^n = \frac{x^k}{(1-x)(1-2x)\dots(1-kx)}. \quad (2.28)$$

Exponential Generating Function

The exponential generating function for the Stirling numbers of the second kind is defined as:

$$E_k(x) = \sum_{n \geq k} S(n, k) \frac{x^n}{n!}, \quad (2.29)$$

By differentiating this definition, we obtain:

$$\frac{d}{dx} E_k(x) = \frac{d}{dx} \sum_{n=k}^{\infty} S(n, k) \frac{x^n}{n!} = \sum_{n=k}^{\infty} S(n, k) \frac{nx^{n-1}}{n!}, \quad (2.30)$$

since $\frac{n}{n!} = \frac{1}{(n-1)!}$, we get:

$$\frac{d}{dx} E_k(x) = \sum_{n=k}^{\infty} S(n, k) \frac{x^{n-1}}{(n-1)!} \quad (2.31)$$

Letting $m = n - 1$ (which means $n = m + 1$ and as n varies from k to ∞ , m varies from $k - 1$ to ∞), this becomes:

$$\frac{d}{dx} E_k(x) = \sum_{m=k-1}^{\infty} S(m+1, k) \frac{x^m}{(m)!}, \quad (2.32)$$

Using the recurrence relation shown earlier (2.18) and multiplying by $\frac{x^m}{m!}$, we find:

$$\sum_{m=k-1}^{\infty} S(m+1, k) \frac{x^m}{(m)!} = \sum_{m=k-1}^{\infty} \left[k S(m, k) + S(m, k-1) \right] \frac{x^m}{m!}. \quad (2.33)$$

For the first term, when $m = k - 1$, note that $S(k - 1, k) = 0$ (Stirling numbers of the second kind are zero when $n < k$), which gives:

$$\sum_{m=k-1}^{\infty} S(m, k) \frac{x^m}{m!} = \sum_{m=k}^{\infty} S(m, k) \frac{x^m}{m!}. \quad (2.34)$$

For the second term, we have:

$$E_{k-1}(x) = \sum_{m=k-1}^{\infty} S(m, k-1) \frac{x^m}{m!}, \quad (2.35)$$

Which finally gives:

$$\frac{d}{dx} E_k(x) = k E_k(x) + E_{k-1}(x). \quad (2.36)$$

It has already been mentioned that $S(0, 0) = 1$ and $S(n, 0) = 0$ for $n \geq 1$, thus:

for $k = 0$:

$$E_0(x) = \sum_{n \geq 0} S(n, 0) \frac{x^n}{n!} = 1, \quad (2.37)$$

for $k = 1$:

$$E_1(x) = \sum_{n \geq 1} S(n, 1) \frac{x^n}{n!} = \sum_{n \geq 1} \frac{x^n}{n!} = e^x - 1, \quad (2.38)$$

by recurrence, we deduce:

$$E_k(x) = \frac{(e^x - 1)^k}{k!}, \quad (2.39)$$

which corresponds to the exponential generating function of the Stirling numbers of the second kind.

2.2 Quantum Mechanics and Stirling Numbers

2.2.1 Heisenberg Algebra

Taking the pair of creation and annihilation operators a^\dagger and a respectively, which satisfy the following commutation relation [16]:

$$[a, a^\dagger] = 1. \quad (2.40)$$

The operators a and a^\dagger , and the relation (2.40), generate the Heisenberg algebra. These operators raise or lower the states of the Hilbert space generated by the number states $|n\rangle$, where $n = 1, 2, \dots$ count the number of particles, or objects in general. The states are assumed to be orthonormal $\langle m|n\rangle = \delta_{mn}$, and constitute a basis of \mathcal{H} ; the representation in this space in this case is called Fock space.

The operators a and a^\dagger , satisfying (2.40), can be realized in the Fock space as already mentioned in Chapter 2:

$$a |n\rangle = \sqrt{n} |n-1\rangle, \quad a^\dagger |n\rangle = \sqrt{n+1} |n+1\rangle. \quad (2.41)$$

The number operator N , which counts the number of particles in a system, is defined by

$$N |n\rangle = n |n\rangle, \quad (2.42)$$

and is represented by:

$$N = a^\dagger a. \quad (2.43)$$

It satisfies the following commutation relations:

$$[a, N] = a, \quad [a^\dagger, N] = -a^\dagger. \quad (2.44)$$

2.2.2 Normal and Anti-normal Ordering and Stirling Numbers

Normal and Anti-normal Ordering

In quantum theory, one often needs to work with operators that are functions of the number operator $\hat{n} = a^\dagger a$, where a and a^\dagger are the annihilation and creation operators respectively. Working with such operator functions is a problem in quantum mechanics due to the non-commutativity of a and a^\dagger ($[a, a^\dagger] = 1$). Therefore, the notion of normal ordering is introduced, which is defined as placing the creation operators to the left and the annihilation operators to the right.

Example:

Consider the example of an operator function $F(a^\dagger, a) = aa^\dagger a$. The goal is to write this operator in normal order, i.e., to arrange the a^\dagger to the left and the a to the right. Using the commutation relation $[a, a^\dagger] = 1$, we have $aa^\dagger = a^\dagger a + 1$. Therefore:

$$F(a^\dagger, a) = aa^\dagger a = (a^\dagger a + 1) a = a^\dagger a^2 + a. \quad (2.45)$$

Now we can say that the operator $F(a^\dagger, a)$ is a normally ordered operator.

Anti-normal ordering consists in rewriting operator products by placing all the annihilation operators a to the left and all the creation operators a^\dagger to the right. This type of ordering, less common than normal ordering, nevertheless plays an important role in certain formulations of quantum mechanics, notably in phase-space representations (such as the Wigner function), the analysis of inverted coherent states, and formal computations in alternative quantizations.

Mathematically, anti-normal ordering reveals deep connections with combinatorial structures such as the Stirling numbers of the first kind, often with alternating signs. This opens the way to combinatorial interpretations of operator expansions, while enriching the understanding of symmetries underlying quantum systems.

Example:

Let the operator $G(a, a^\dagger) = a^\dagger a a^\dagger$:

$$G(a, a^\dagger) = (a a^\dagger - 1) a^\dagger = a(a^\dagger)^2 - a^\dagger, \quad (2.46)$$

the operator G is anti-normally ordered.

Normal and Anti-normal Ordering in Relation to Stirling Numbers

To present the connection between normal ordering and Stirling numbers, let us compute the number operator $\hat{n} = a^\dagger a$ raised to different powers, i.e., express the normal order of \hat{n}^m as mentioned in [17].

For $m = 2$:

$$\hat{n}^2 = (a^\dagger a) (a^\dagger a) = a^\dagger a a^\dagger a, \quad (2.47)$$

using the fact that $a a^\dagger = a^\dagger a + 1$, we obtain:

$$\hat{n}^2 = a^\dagger (a^\dagger a + 1) a = [a^\dagger]^2 a^2 + a^\dagger a, \quad (2.48)$$

so for $m = 2$, we have:

$$\hat{n}^2 = [a^\dagger]^2 a^2 + a^\dagger a. \quad (2.49)$$

For $m = 3$:

$$\hat{n}^3 = [a^\dagger]^3 a^3 + 3[a^\dagger]^2 a^2 + a^\dagger a. \quad (2.50)$$

For $m = 4$:

$$\hat{n}^4 = [a^\dagger]^4 a^4 + 6[a^\dagger]^3 a^3 + 7[a^\dagger]^2 a^2 + a^\dagger a. \quad (2.51)$$

What we can conclude from this is that the numbers that appear at each iteration m are the Stirling numbers of the second kind, as shown in the following table already mentioned in (2.1.3).

From this we can generalize the normal order of n^m using the following relation [17]:

$$n^m = \sum_{k=0}^m S(m, k) [a^\dagger]^k a^k. \quad (2.52)$$

By doing the same reasoning for normal order, we can deduce the formula that reveals the Stirling numbers of the second kind for the anti-normally ordered operator $N = a^\dagger a$:

$$n^m = \sum_{k=0}^m (-1)^{m-k} S(m+1, k+1) a^k [a^\dagger]^k. \quad (2.53)$$

Representations on Number Bases and Coherent States

Let the coherent state be defined by $|z\rangle = D(z)|0\rangle$, where $D(z) = e^{z a^\dagger - z^* a}$ is the displacement operator, and $|0\rangle$ is the vacuum state.

We want to compute:

$$\langle z|e^{-\gamma n}|z\rangle = e^\gamma \langle z| \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \frac{(1-e^\gamma)^m}{m!} a^m (a^\dagger)^m |z\rangle, \quad (2.54)$$

using:

$$\langle z|a^m (a^\dagger)^m |z\rangle = \langle 0|(a+z)^m (a^\dagger+z^*)^m |0\rangle, \quad (2.55)$$

which yields:

$$\sum_{k=0}^m |z|^{2k} \left(\frac{m!}{(m-k)!k!} \right)^2 (m-k)!, \quad (2.56)$$

thus we can write:

$$\langle z|e^{-\gamma n}|z\rangle = e^\gamma \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} (1-e^\gamma)^m L_m(-|z|^2), \quad (2.57)$$

where $L_m(x)$ denotes the Laguerre polynomials of order m . Finally, we obtain a closed-form expression:

$$\langle z|e^{-\gamma n}|z\rangle = \exp(|z|^2(e^{-\gamma} - 1)). \quad (2.58)$$

For the Fock states $|n\rangle$, we have:

$$\begin{aligned} \langle n|e^{-\gamma n}|n\rangle &= e^\gamma \langle n| \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \frac{(1-e^\gamma)^m}{m!} a^m (a^\dagger)^m |n\rangle \\ &= e^\gamma \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \frac{(1-e^\gamma)^m}{m!} \frac{(m+n)!}{n!}. \end{aligned} \quad (2.59)$$

Setting $k = n + m$, we rewrite the sum:

$$\langle n|e^{-\gamma n}|n\rangle = e^\gamma \sum_{k=n}^{\infty} \frac{(1-e^\gamma)^{k-n}}{k!} \frac{k!}{n!(k-n)!}, \quad (2.60)$$

which gives the closed-form expression:

$$\langle n|e^{-\gamma n}|n\rangle = e^{-\gamma n}. \quad (2.61)$$

2.3 Generalization to q-Deformation

2.3.1 q-Deformed Stirling Numbers

Among the generalizations of the Heisenberg algebra, there is the q-deformed Heisenberg algebra. The number operator \hat{n} itself is replaced by a q-deformed bosonic number operator due to this algebra, following the approach of Jacob Katriel and Maurice Kibler [18]. We will later revisit the properties of this algebra.

Let us first define the deformed numbers. A deformed number of M-Type is given by:

$$[x]_M = \frac{q^x - 1}{q - 1}. \quad (2.62)$$

There are other types of deformed numbers, P-Type and G-Type respectively:

$$[x]_P = \frac{q^x - q^{-x}}{q - q^{-1}} \quad \text{and} \quad [x]_G = \frac{q^x - p^x}{q - p}, \quad (2.63)$$

$[x]_M$ and $[x]_P$ are special cases of $[x]_G$. When $p = 1$, we obtain $[x]_M$, and when $p = q^{-1}$, $[x]_G$ becomes $[x]_P$.

The combinatorial definitions of the Stirling numbers of the first and second kind are given by:

$$x(x-1)\dots\dots\dots(x-k+1) = \sum_{m=1}^k s_q(k, m)x^m, \quad (2.64)$$

$$x^m = \sum_{k=1}^m S(m, k)x(x-1)\dots\dots\dots(x-k+1), \quad (2.65)$$

with $s(k, m)$ and $S(m, k)$ being the Stirling numbers of the first and second kind respectively. For the q-deformed algebra, the numbers x are replaced by the deformed numbers $[x]_M$. The two definitions (2.64) and (2.65) are rewritten as:

$$[x]_M[x-1]_M\dots\dots\dots[x-k+1]_M = \sum_{m=1}^k s_q(k, m)[x]_M^m, \quad (2.66)$$

$$[x]_M^m = \sum_{k=1}^m S(m, k)[x]_M[x-1]_M\dots\dots\dots[x-k+1]_M. \quad (2.67)$$

2.3.2 Recurrence Relation:

Recall that the classical recurrence formulas for Stirling numbers of the first and second kind are respectively given by:

$$s(k+1) = s(k, m+1) - ks(k, m), \quad (2.68)$$

$$S(m+1, k) = S(m, k-1) + kS(m, k). \quad (2.69)$$

Now the goal is to find the recurrence formula for the deformed Stirling numbers of the first and second kind.

Let us start with the Stirling numbers of the first kind. From the definition (2.66) of the deformed Stirling numbers of the first kind, multiplying both sides of equation (2.66) by $[x-k]_M$ yields:

$$[x]_M[x-1]_M \dots [x-k]_M = \sum_{m=1}^{k+1} s_q(k+1, m)[x]_M^m, \quad (2.70)$$

$$[x]_M[x-1]_M \dots [x-k]_M = \sum_{m=1}^k s_q(k, m)[x]_M^m[x-k]_M, \quad (2.71)$$

from (2.70) and (2.71) we conclude:

$$\sum_{m=1}^{k+1} s_q(k+1, m)[x]_M^m = \sum_{m=1}^k s_q(k, m)[x]_M^m[x-k]_M. \quad (2.72)$$

Using the following property of deformed numbers:

$$[x-k]_M = q^{-k}([x]_M - [k]_M), \quad (2.73)$$

equation (2.72) becomes:

$$\sum_{m=1}^{k+1} s_q(k+1, m)[x]_M^m = q^{-k} \left(\sum_{m=1}^k s_q(k, m)[x]_M^{m+1} - \sum_{m=1}^k s_q(k, m)[k]_M[x]_M^m \right). \quad (2.74)$$

By making a change of variable $m' = m + 1$ in the first term on the left-hand side of (2.74), it becomes:

$$\sum_{m=1}^{k+1} s_q(k+1, m)[x]_M^m = q^{-k} \left(\sum_{m=2}^k s_q(k, m-1)[x]_M^m - [k]_M \sum_{m=1}^k s_q(k, m)[x]_M^m \right), \quad (2.75)$$

which finally yields:

$$\sum_{m=1}^{k+1} s_q(k+1, m)[x]_M^m = q^{-k} \sum_{m=1}^k (s_q(k, m-1) - [k]_M s_q(k, m)) [x]_M^m, \quad (2.76)$$

which leads us to the recurrence formula for the deformed Stirling numbers of the

first kind:

$$s_q(k+1, m) = q^{-k} (s_q(k, m-1) - [k]_M s_q(k, m)). \quad (2.77)$$

For the deformed Stirling numbers of the second kind, we find:

$$S(m+1, k) = q^{k-1} S(m, k-1) + [k]_M S(m, k). \quad (2.78)$$

2.3.3 Orthogonality Relation:

The inverse or orthogonality relation allows us to move from expansions in classical powers to expansions in terms of falling factorials—a classical transformation in combinatorics and series analysis.

Taking the two definitions of $s_q(k, m)$ and $S_q(m, k)$ (2.66) (2.67):

$$[x]_M^k = \sum_{m=1}^k s_q(k, m) [x]_M^m, \quad (2.79)$$

$$[x]_M^m = \sum_{k'=1}^m S(m, k') [x]_M^{k'}, \quad (2.80)$$

the passage from $s_q(k, m)$ to $S_q(m, k)$ is done via a change of basis from $\{[x]_M^m\}$ to $\{[x]_M^{m'}\}$. Replacing (2.80) into (2.79), we obtain:

$$[x]_M^k = \sum_{m=1}^k s_q(k, m) \left(\sum_{k'=1}^m S(m, k') [x]_M^{k'} \right), \quad (2.81)$$

which gives:

$$[x]_M^k = \sum_{m=1}^k \left(\sum_{k'=1}^m s_q(k, m) S(m, k') \right) [x]_M^{k'}. \quad (2.82)$$

For the equality to hold, it must be that:

$$\sum_{m=1}^k \left(\sum_{k'=1}^m s_q(k, m) S(m, k') \right) = 1, \quad (2.83)$$

which yields:

$$\sum_{m=1}^k s_q(k, m) S(m, k') = \delta(k, k'). \quad (2.84)$$

2.3.4 q -Deformed Coherent States and q -Stirling Numbers

The q -deformed coherent states generalize the standard coherent states of the quantum formalism by taking into account a deformation of the Heisenberg algebra. They natu-

rally appear in quantum systems with non-classical symmetries (quantum groups, spin chains, deformed oscillators, etc.) [19, 20, 21], and are strongly related to q -deformed Stirling numbers through their combinatorial structure [22, 23].

We consider the operators a , a^\dagger and \hat{N} satisfying the q -deformed commutation relation:

$$aa^\dagger - qa^\dagger a = 1, \quad (2.85)$$

according to the convention adopted in the literature [19, 20]. This deformation profoundly modifies the structure of Fock space and the construction of coherent states.

A q -deformed coherent state is defined as a Fock vector of the form:

$$|z\rangle_q = \mathcal{N}_q(|z|^2)^{-\frac{1}{2}} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{z^n}{\sqrt{[n]_q!}} |n\rangle_q, \quad (2.86)$$

where $z \in \mathbb{C}$, $[n]_q! = [1]_q[2]_q \cdots [n]_q$, and $[n]_q = \frac{1-q^n}{1-q}$ is the q -integer. The normalization \mathcal{N}_q ensures that $\langle \alpha | \alpha \rangle_q = 1$ [24, 25].

These states are eigenvectors of the annihilation operator:

$$a |z\rangle_q = z |z\rangle_q, \quad (2.87)$$

as in the standard case, but their series expansion encodes a q -combinatorial structure.

Consider the observable $(a^\dagger a)^n$, which plays a fundamental role in expectation value calculations:

$$\langle z | (a^\dagger a)^n | z \rangle_q. \quad (2.88)$$

To evaluate it, we express it in normal order:

$$(a^\dagger a)^n = \sum_{k=1}^n S_q(n, k) (a^\dagger)^k a^k, \quad (2.89)$$

where the coefficients $S_q(n, k)$ are the q -deformed Stirling numbers of the second kind [22, 23].

Thus, we obtain:

$$\langle z | (a^\dagger a)^n | z \rangle_q = \sum_{k=1}^n S_q(n, k) |z|^{2k}. \quad (2.90)$$

This shows that the n th-order moments of the occupation number are expressed in terms of $S_q(n, k)$ and $|z|^2$, allowing the analysis of quantum fluctuations in q -deformed coherent states. Unlike classical coherent states, the moments no longer follow an exact Poisson law, but a q -Poisson law dependent on the deformation [25].

The presence of q -deformed Stirling numbers reflects the deformed quantum nature of the coherent state. They capture the modification of the internal partition structure

of $(a^\dagger a)^n$ due to the q -deformed non-commutativity.

In particular:

- For $q \rightarrow 1$, we recover the classical Stirling numbers and the standard results of the harmonic oscillator.
- For $q < 1$ or $q > 1$, the states exhibit non-classical behavior such as sub- or super-dispersion [26].

This formalism has applications in the description of quantum oscillators in non-commutative geometry, in q -deformed field theory, or in deformed quantum optics [27, 24].

2.3.5 Applications

The q -deformed Stirling numbers are a powerful tool in the study of systems with deformed symmetry or non-classical thermodynamic behavior. They naturally arise in contexts where standard algebraic structures (such as the Heisenberg algebra) are generalized to include a deformation parameter q , allowing exploration of new physical regimes.

Statistical Physics and q -Deformed Entropy

Tsallis' approach to non-extensive statistical mechanics is based on a generalization of the exponential function defined by:

$$\exp_q(x) = [1 + (1 - q)x]_+^{\frac{1}{1-q}}, \quad (2.91)$$

where $q \in \mathbb{R}$ is the entropy parameter. This function appears in the definition of new generating functions associated with deformed Touchard polynomials, and hence with the deformed Stirling numbers of the second kind $S_{p,q}(n, k)$.

The (p, q) -deformed Touchard polynomials are defined by the generating series:

$$\exp_p(x (\exp_q(t) - 1)) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} T_n(x; p, q) \frac{t^n}{n!}, \quad (2.92)$$

where:

$$\exp_p(x) = [1 + (1 - p)x]_+^{\frac{1}{1-p}}, \quad Q_n(q) = \prod_{j=1}^n (jq - (j - 1)) \quad (2.93)$$

The first polynomials are:

$$\begin{aligned} T_0(x; p, q) &= 1, \\ T_1(x; p, q) &= x, \\ T_2(x; p, q) &= xq + x^2p. \end{aligned}$$

These polynomials satisfy a non-trivial recurrence:

$$T_{n+1}(x; p, q) = xQ_n(q) + x \sum_{m=1}^n \left[\binom{n}{m} - (1-p) \binom{n}{m-1} \right] Q_{n-m}(q) T_m(x; p, q). \quad (2.94)$$

The (p, q) -deformed Stirling numbers of the second kind $S_{p,q}(n, k)$ are defined as the coefficients of the polynomials $T_n(x; p, q)$:

$$T_n(x; p, q) = \sum_{k=0}^n S_{p,q}(n, k) x^k. \quad (2.95)$$

They satisfy the following recurrence relation:

$$S_{p,q}(n+1, k) = [1 - (1-p)(k-1)] S_{p,q}(n, k-1) + [k - (1-q)n] S_{p,q}(n, k), \quad (2.96)$$

with $S_{p,q}(0, 0) = 1$.

The Tsallis exponential function $\exp_q(x)$ is directly related to the non-extensive entropy:

$$S_q = \frac{1 - \sum_i p_i^q}{q-1}.$$

Using the structure of set partitions with internal statistics, the Stirling numbers $S_{p,q}(n, k)$ appear as counting weighted ordered partitions with parameters (p, q) related to generalized entropies:

$$S_{p,q}(n, k) = \sum_{\pi \in \text{DOP}_{n,k}} (p-1)^{\text{nsb}(\pi)} (q-1)^{\text{nse}(\pi)}, \quad (2.97)$$

where $\text{DOP}_{n,k}$ denotes the set of doubly ordered partitions of $[n]$ into k blocks, with $\text{nsb}(\pi)$ and $\text{nse}(\pi)$ two statistics on these partitions.

The exponential generating function of $S_{p,q}(n, k)$ is given by:

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} S_{p,q}(n, k) \frac{t^n}{n!} = Q_{k-1}(p) \frac{(\exp_q(t) - 1)^k}{k!}. \quad (2.98)$$

These results show a close relationship between Tsallis generalized entropies, set partitions with internal structure, and q -deformed Stirling numbers. They provide a natural mathematical foundation for studying non-extensive distributions in statistical mechanics.

Quantum Groups and Hopf Algebras

Another essential application of q -deformed Stirling numbers is their appearance in the structure of quantum groups, which are deformations of classical Lie groups. These

objects, introduced by Drinfeld and Jimbo in the 1980s, play a fundamental role in the exact solution of integrable models in statistical physics and field theory.

In this context, the creation and annihilation operators satisfy q -deformed commutation relations such as:

$$aa^\dagger - qa^\dagger a = 1,$$

and the associated algebra becomes a Hopf algebra. Operator developments (particularly normal and antinormal order) in these algebras naturally reveal coefficients which are precisely the q -deformed Stirling numbers [28, 29].

In particular, these coefficients appear in expressions of powers of the number operator $N = a^\dagger a$ in terms of normal products, allowing us to relate physical observables to the underlying combinatorial structures. This opens the way to explicit calculations in models such as spin chains, deformed Bose gases, or representations of quantum groups $U_q(\mathfrak{su}(2))$.

Chapter 3

Examples of Stirling Operators Associated with Quantum Systems

3.1 Generalized Heisenberg Algebra and Fock Space

3.1.1 Commutation Relation and Casimir Operator

The generalized Heisenberg algebra introduced by Curado and Rego-Monteiro in [30] is defined by the creation operator a^\dagger and annihilation operator a , as well as the Hamiltonian H such that:

$$aH = f(H) a, \quad (3.1)$$

$$Ha^\dagger = a^\dagger f(H), \quad (3.2)$$

where a^\dagger is the Hermitian conjugate of a and the Hamiltonian H is self-adjoint. The function $f(H)$ is an analytic function of H , called the characteristic function of the algebra. A large class of Heisenberg-type algebras can be obtained simply by choosing an appropriate function $f(H)$. Similarly, the commutation relation between a and a^\dagger is given by:

$$[a, a^\dagger] = f(H) - H. \quad (3.3)$$

Note that this generalized algebra has a Casimir given by:

$$C = aa^\dagger - f(H) = a^\dagger a - H. \quad (3.4)$$

This can be shown starting from the standard definition of the Casimir operator:

$$C = a^\dagger a - H, \quad (3.5)$$

using (3.1) and (3.3), we get:

$$\begin{aligned}
C &= a^\dagger a - H \\
&= aa^\dagger - f(H) + H - H \\
&= a^\dagger a - f(H).
\end{aligned} \tag{3.6}$$

This shows that the generalized operator is indeed a Casimir, i.e., it satisfies the following commutation relations:

$$[C, H] = 0, \quad [C, a] = 0 \quad \text{and} \quad [C, a^\dagger] = 0, \tag{3.7}$$

Taking (3.1) and multiplying on the left by a^\dagger , we obtain:

$$a^\dagger a H = a^\dagger f(H) a, \tag{3.8}$$

Using (3.2), we find:

$$a^\dagger a H = H a^\dagger a, \tag{3.9}$$

which gives:

$$[H, aa^\dagger] = 0 \implies [H, C] = 0. \tag{3.10}$$

For the commutation with a , we compute:

$$\begin{aligned}
[C, a] &= [aa^\dagger - f(H), a] = a(aa^\dagger - f(H)) - (aa^\dagger - f(H))a \\
&= a(aa^\dagger - a^\dagger a) + f(H)a - af(H) \\
&= a(f(H) - H) - a(f(H) - H) \\
&= 0,
\end{aligned} \tag{3.11}$$

where in the penultimate equality we used (3.1) and (3.3). Similarly for a^\dagger , it is easy to show that:

$$[C, a^\dagger] = 0, \tag{3.12}$$

which proves the relations in (3.7).

3.1.2 Reformulation of the Generalized Heisenberg Algebra

The generalized Heisenberg algebra (GHA) introduced in the previous section has been recently reformulated by Tahri and Ouahhabi [7], by introducing the notion of quantum operator functions, denoted $[k]_f(H)$. These are defined from the characteristic function $f(H)$ as follows:

$$[k]_f(H) = f^k(H) - H, \tag{3.13}$$

where $f^k(H)$ denotes the k -th iteration of f , that is:

$$f^k = \underbrace{f \circ f \circ \cdots \circ f}_{k\text{-times}}, \quad (3.14)$$

with $f^0(H) = H$. For $k = 1$, we then have:

$$[1]_f(H) = f(H) - H, \quad (3.15)$$

which will be used subsequently in the rewriting of the generalized commutation relation. Using the quantum operator function defined previously, the generalized commutation relation (3.3) can now be written in a compact form as:

$$[a, a^\dagger] = [1]_f(H). \quad (3.16)$$

More generally, it can be shown that for a^k and $(a^\dagger)^k$, we have:

$$[a^k, a^\dagger] = [k]_f(H)a^{k-1}, \quad \text{and} \quad [a, (a^\dagger)^k] = (a^\dagger)^{k-1}[k]_f(H), \quad (3.17)$$

We also write:

$$a^k [n]_f(H) = [n]_f(f^k(H)) \tilde{a}^k, \quad (3.18)$$

$$[n]_f(H) (a^\dagger)^k = (a^\dagger)^k [n]_f(f^k(H)), \quad (3.19)$$

When $f(H) = H + 1$, we immediately recover the standard commutation relation of the harmonic oscillator:

$$[1]_f(H) = H + 1 - H \implies [a, a^\dagger] = 1. \quad (3.20)$$

But in the general case, $[1]_f(H)$ may depend on H . This formalism is fundamental for the study of generalized normal ordering as well as for the definition of generalized Stirling operators, which will be addressed in the following sections.

Let us now consider some examples of quantum systems, in particular the case of the harmonic oscillator and a q -deformed system.

Harmonic oscillator:

In the case of the harmonic oscillator, the characteristic function associated with the system is given by:

$$f(H) = H + 1. \quad (3.21)$$

This expression allows the commutation relation (3.3) to be rewritten as:

$$[a, a^\dagger] = H + 1 - H = 1. \quad (3.22)$$

This is the standard commutation relation defining the Heisenberg algebra.

q-deformed harmonic oscillator:

In the case of q -deformation, the characteristic function associated with the system is written as:

$$f(H) = qH + 1, \quad (3.23)$$

where q is a real (or complex) parameter distinct from 1. Using this function, the commutation relation (3.3) becomes:

$$[a, a^\dagger] = (q - 1)H + 1. \quad (3.24)$$

This expression modifies the algebraic structure of the system and constitutes a generalization of the standard commutation relation.

3.1.3 Representation in Fock Space

The representation in Fock space is based on the introduction of the orthonormal basis $\{|m\rangle, m \in \mathbf{N}\}$ of eigenvectors of the Hamiltonian H with corresponding eigenvalues, denoted α_m such that:

$$H |m\rangle = \alpha_m |m\rangle. \quad (3.25)$$

We write the action of the operators a^\dagger and a as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} a^\dagger |m\rangle &= N_m |m+1\rangle, \\ a |m\rangle &= N_{m-1} |m-1\rangle, \end{aligned} \quad (3.26)$$

thus:

$$a^\dagger a |m\rangle = N_{m-1}^2 |m\rangle. \quad (3.27)$$

Using the commutation relations defining the generalized Heisenberg algebra (3.1) and (3.2), we obtain:

$$aH |m\rangle = \alpha_m N_{m-1} |m-1\rangle, \quad (3.28)$$

$$aH |m\rangle = f(H) a |m\rangle = N_{m-1} f(\alpha_{m-1}) |m-1\rangle. \quad (3.29)$$

Comparing the two equations (3.28) and (3.29), we conclude that:

$$\alpha_m = f(\alpha_{m-1}), \quad (3.30)$$

where $m - 1$ and m represent two successive energy levels. Thus, by iteration, all energy levels can be obtained from the ground level α_0 :

$$f^m(\alpha_0) = \alpha_m. \quad (3.31)$$

Now let us compute N_m , we have:

$$\langle m|a^\dagger a|m\rangle = N_{m-1}^2, \quad (3.32)$$

on the other hand:

$$\begin{aligned} \langle m|aa^\dagger|m\rangle &= N_m^2 \\ &= \langle m|a^\dagger a + f(H) - H|m\rangle \\ &= N_{m-1}^2 + f(\alpha_m) - \alpha_m, \end{aligned} \quad (3.33)$$

hence the following recurrence relation:

$$\begin{aligned} N_m^2 - \alpha_{m+1} &= N_{m-1}^2 - \alpha_m \\ &= N_{-1} - \alpha_0, \end{aligned} \quad (3.34)$$

which gives, taking into account that $N_{-1} = 0$:

$$\begin{aligned} N_m^2 &= f^{m+1}(\alpha_0) - \alpha_0 \\ &= [m+1]_f(\alpha_0), \end{aligned} \quad (3.35)$$

hence we also write:

$$N_{m-1}^2 = [m]_f(\alpha_0), \quad (3.36)$$

which modifies the action on the Fock basis $\{|m\rangle\}$:

$$\begin{aligned} a|m\rangle &= \sqrt{[m]_f(\alpha_0)}|m-1\rangle, \\ a^\dagger|m\rangle &= \sqrt{[m+1]_f(\alpha_0)}|m+1\rangle. \end{aligned} \quad (3.37)$$

The f -analog of the operator action $N_f = a^\dagger a$ is:

$$N_f|m\rangle = [m]_f(\alpha_0)|m\rangle. \quad (3.38)$$

Finally, let us rewrite the Hamiltonian H in the generalized case. From (3.35) and (3.36), we write:

$$\alpha_m = \alpha_0 + [m]_f(\alpha_0), \quad (3.39)$$

which allows expressing H as:

$$H = N_f + \alpha_0. \quad (3.40)$$

3.2 Recurrence Relation of Generalized Stirling Operators and Explicit Solutions

Katriel showed [31] that the Stirling numbers of the second kind appear as coefficients in the expansion of the n th power of the number operator in normal order. Then, by considering the q -deformed Heisenberg algebra generated by (a, a^\dagger, N) , the authors of [32] showed that the generalization of these coefficients consists in treating them as functions of the generalized operator N . The generalized Stirling operators $S_f(n, k)(H)$, introduced in the normally ordered expansion of N_f^n 3.41, possess a particularly explicit expression which generalizes classical combinatorial formulas.

We now introduce the following definition:

$$N_f^n = (a^\dagger a)^n = \sum_{k=0}^n S_f(n, k)(H) (a^\dagger)^k a^k, \quad (3.41)$$

where $S_f(n, k)(H)$ are the generalized Stirling operators. They satisfy the initial conditions:

$$\begin{cases} S_f(n, 0)(H) = \delta_{n,0} \mathbb{I}, \\ S_f(n, k)(H) = 0 \quad \text{if } k > n. \end{cases} \quad (3.42)$$

Now, taking equation (3.41) and writing it for $n + 1$, we get:

$$N_f^{n+1} = (a^\dagger a)(a^\dagger a)^n = \sum_{k=0}^{n+1} S_f(n+1, k)(H) (a^\dagger)^k a^k, \quad (3.43)$$

Using the commutation relation given in (3.17) and (3.19), we obtain:

$$\begin{aligned} N_f^{n+1} &= \sum_{k=0}^n S_f(n, k)(H) a^\dagger \left[(a^\dagger)^{k-1} [k]_f(H) + (a^\dagger)^k a \right] a^k \\ &= \sum_{k=0}^n S_f(n, k)(H) (a^\dagger)^{k+1} a^{k+1} + \sum_{k=0}^n S_f(n, k)(H) (a^\dagger)^k [k]_f(H) a^k \\ &\stackrel{(3.40)}{=} \sum_{k=0}^{n+1} S_f(n, k)(H) (a^\dagger)^{k+1} a^{k+1} + \sum_{k=0}^{n+1} (k)_f(H) S_f(n, k-1)(H) (a^\dagger)^k a^k. \end{aligned} \quad (3.44)$$

By comparing (3.43) and (3.44) and identifying the coefficients, we obtain the following recurrence relation for the generalized Stirling operators:

$$S_f(n+1, k)(H) = S_f(n, k-1)(H) + (k)_f(H) S_f(n, k)(H). \quad (3.45)$$

where $(k)_f(H)$ are the quantum operator functions defined by:

$$(k)_f(H) := [k]_f(f^{-k}(H)) = H - f^{-k}(H). \quad (3.46)$$

An explicit expression of the operators $S_f(n, k)(H)$ is given by:

$$S_f(n, k)(H) = \sum_{0 \leq p_{n-k} \leq \dots \leq p_1 \leq k} \prod_{i=1}^{n-k} (p_i)_f(H). \quad (3.47)$$

This expression indeed satisfies the recurrence relation (3.45). We have:

$$\begin{aligned} S_f(n+1, k)(H) &= \sum_{0 \leq p_{n+1-k} \leq p_{n-k} \leq \dots \leq p_1 \leq k} \prod_{i=1}^{n+1-k} (p_i)_f(H) \\ &= \sum_{p_1=0}^{k-1} (p_1)_f(H) \sum_{0 \leq p_{n+1-k} \leq \dots \leq p_2 \leq p_1} \prod_{i=2}^{n+1-k} (p_i)_f(H) \\ &\quad + (k)_f(H) \sum_{0 \leq p_{n+1-k} \leq \dots \leq p_2 \leq k} \prod_{i=2}^{n+1-k} (p_i)_f(H) \\ &= \sum_{0 \leq p_{n+1-k} \leq \dots \leq p_1 \leq k-1} \prod_{i=1}^{n+1-k} (p_i)_f(H) \\ &\quad + (k)_f(H) \sum_{0 \leq p'_{n-k} \leq \dots \leq p'_1 \leq k} \prod_{i=1}^{n-k} (p'_i)_f(H). \end{aligned} \quad (3.48)$$

It can also be written in symmetric form:

$$S_f(n, k)(H) = \sum_{s_1 + \dots + s_k = n-k} (1)_f(H)^{s_1} (2)_f(H)^{s_2} \dots (k)_f(H)^{s_k}, \quad (3.49)$$

which generalizes the classical representation of Stirling numbers as complete symmetric polynomials.

Remark:

When $f(H) = H + 1$, we have $f^{-k}(H) = H - k$, and thus:

$$(k)_f(H) = H - (H - k) = k \cdot \mathbb{I}, \quad (3.50)$$

which shows that the operators $S_f(n, k)(H)$ reduce to classical Stirling numbers multiplied by the identity operator:

$$S_f(n, k)(H) = \left[\sum_{0 \leq p_{n-k} \leq \dots \leq p_1 \leq k} \prod_{i=1}^{n-k} p_i \right] 1 = S(n, k) \cdot \mathbb{I}. \quad (3.51)$$

This formulation thus justifies the transition from scalar coefficients to operator functions in the framework of the generalized algebra.

This allows us to write the commutation relation using 3.16 and 3.64.

These formulas take on more concrete meaning when applied to specific quantum systems.

3.3 Application Examples

3.3.1 Potential of the Hydrogen Atom

Overview of the Energy Spectrum

The hydrogen atom constitutes one of the fundamental systems in quantum physics, not only due to its simplicity — a proton and an electron — but also because of its historical role in the development of quantum theory. One of the major features of this system is the quantization of its energy spectrum, which radically differs from the classical prediction of a continuous spectrum.

In classical mechanics, an electron orbiting a nucleus could occupy orbits of any energy. This would imply a continuous emission of radiation and a gradual fall of the electron toward the nucleus. However, experiments show that the hydrogen atom only emits (or absorbs) specific well-defined spectral lines, thus revealing a discrete spectrum [33].

This discretization was first explained by Bohr's model (1913), in which he postulated that the electron could only occupy certain stable orbits, characterized by a quantized angular momentum [34]:

$$L = n\hbar, \quad n \in \mathbb{N}^* \quad (3.52)$$

This hypothesis made it possible to recover the energy levels:

$$E_n = -\frac{13,6 \text{ eV}}{n^2}, \quad n = 1, 2, 3, \dots \quad (3.53)$$

This formula, although based on semi-classical arguments, correctly described the Balmer series lines and other atomic transitions [35].

The true justification of this quantization came with quantum mechanics, particularly with the resolution of the Schrödinger equation for the Coulomb potential [36]:

$$V(r) = -\frac{e^2}{4\pi\epsilon_0 r}. \quad (3.54)$$

In this framework, the electron state is described by a wave function $\psi_{n,\ell,m}(r, \theta, \phi)$,

solution of the Schrödinger equation depending on the quantum numbers:

- n : principal quantum number,
- ℓ : orbital angular momentum,
- m : angular momentum projection.

The separation of variables in this equation leads to boundary conditions that allow solutions only for discrete energy values. The spectrum of bound states is therefore quantized:

$$E_n = -\frac{m_e e^4}{8\varepsilon_0^2 h^2 n^2} = -\frac{13,6 \text{ eV}}{n^2}. \quad (3.55)$$

This quantization reflects the fact that the eigenstate space of the Hamiltonian is non-continuous: bound states are associated with discrete eigenvalues, while unbound states (ionization states) form a continuous spectrum.

The origin of quantization is therefore structural: it directly stems from the mathematical structure of the operators (Hamiltonian, angular momentum) and the boundary conditions imposed on the physical wave functions. This phenomenon perfectly illustrates how quantum theory transforms classical notions: energy is no longer a free parameter but an operator spectrum.

Generalized Heisenberg Algebra

The energy spectrum of the dimensionless hydrogen atom potential is given by $\alpha_m = -\frac{1}{m^2}$ with $m \in \mathbb{N}^*$, which can equivalently be written as $\alpha_m = -\frac{1}{(m+1)^2}$ where $m \in \mathbb{N}$. Let us now look for the characteristic function of this system $f_{ha}(\alpha_m)$:

$$f_{ha}(\alpha_m) = -\frac{1}{[(m+1)+1]^2} = -\frac{1}{[(m+1)^2 + 2(m+1) + 1]}, \quad (3.56)$$

in terms of α_m , we obtain:

$$f_{ha}(\alpha_m) = \frac{\alpha_m}{\left(1 + 2\sqrt{-\alpha_m} + (\sqrt{-\alpha_m})^2\right)} = \frac{\alpha_m}{(\sqrt{-\alpha_m} + 1)^2}, \quad (3.57)$$

which gives:

$$f_{ha}^k(\alpha_m) = \frac{\alpha_m}{(k\sqrt{-\alpha_m} + 1)^2}, \quad (3.58)$$

consequently, in terms of H we have:

$$f_{ha}^k(H) = \frac{H}{(k\sqrt{-H} + 1)^2}. \quad (3.59)$$

Let us now compute the inverse of the characteristic function. From (3.57), we can write:

$$(\sqrt{-\alpha_m} + 1)^2 f_{ha}(\alpha_m) = \alpha_m, \quad (3.60)$$

knowing that $f(\alpha_m) < 0$ and $\alpha_m < 0$, we obtain:

$$(\sqrt{-\alpha_m} + 1) \sqrt{-f(\alpha_m)} = \sqrt{-\alpha_m}, \quad (3.61)$$

which gives:

$$\sqrt{-\alpha_m} = \frac{\sqrt{-f_{ha}(\alpha_m)}}{(1 - \sqrt{-f_{ha}(\alpha_m)})}. \quad (3.62)$$

Let $\beta_m = f_{ha}^{-1}(\alpha_m)$, we obtain:

$$f_{ha}^{-1}(\alpha_m) = \frac{\alpha_m}{(1 - \sqrt{-\alpha_m})^2}. \quad (3.63)$$

Thus we can iteratively compute $f_{ha}^{-k}(\alpha_m)$; indeed, a simple calculation gives:

$$f_{ha}^{-k}(H) = \frac{H}{(1 - k\sqrt{-H})^2}. \quad (3.64)$$

The quantum operator functions associated with the hydrogen atom potential are obtained from (3.59) and (3.64), their expressions are respectively given by:

$$\begin{aligned} [k]_{f_{ha}}(H) &= f_{ha}^k(H) - H \\ &= \frac{kH(kH - 2\sqrt{-H})}{(1 + k\sqrt{-H})^2}, \end{aligned} \quad (3.65)$$

$$\begin{aligned} (k)_{f_{ha}}(H) &= H - f_{ha}^{-k}(H) \\ &= -\frac{kH(2\sqrt{-H} + kH)}{(1 - k\sqrt{-H})^2}, \end{aligned} \quad (3.66)$$

which allows us to write the commutation relation using (3.16) (3.64):

$$[a, a^\dagger] = [1]_{f_{ha}}(H) = \frac{H(H - 2\sqrt{-H})}{(\sqrt{-H} + 1)^2}. \quad (3.67)$$

Let us now determine the action of N_f on $|m\rangle$ for the case of the hydrogen atom potential. Using (3.65), we write $[m]_{f_{ha}}(\alpha_0)$ as:

$$[m]_{f_{ha}}(\alpha_0) = \frac{m\alpha_0(m\alpha_0 - 2\sqrt{-\alpha_0})}{(1 + m\sqrt{-\alpha_0})^2}, \quad (3.68)$$

taking $\alpha_0 = -1$, we obtain:

$$[m]_{f_{ha}}(\alpha_0) = \frac{m(2+m)}{(1+m)^2} = 1 - \frac{1}{(1+m)^2}. \quad (3.69)$$

thus we can also write:

$$[[m]_{f_{ha}}(\alpha_0)]^n = \sum_{k=0}^n S_{f_{ha}}(n, k, m) [[m]_{f_{ha}}(\alpha_0)]^k, \quad (3.70)$$

where $[[m]_{f_{ha}}(\alpha_0)]^k = [m]_{f_{ha}}(\alpha_0)[m-1]_{f_{ha}}(\alpha_0) \dots [m-k+1]_{f_{ha}}(\alpha_0)$ is the generalized falling factorial.

Stirling Operators for the Hydrogen Atom Potential

Let us now compute the Stirling operators. Using equation (3.47), we obtain:

$$S_{f_{ha}}(n, k)(H) = (-1)^{n-k} \sum_{0 \leq p_{n-k} \leq \dots \leq p_1 \leq k} \prod_{i=1}^{n-k} \left[\frac{p_i H (p_i H + 2\sqrt{-H})}{(1 - p_i \sqrt{-H})^2} \right]. \quad (3.71)$$

Let us explicitly give the Stirling operators for $1 \leq n, k \leq 4$.

$$\begin{aligned} S_{f_{ha}}(n, 1)(H) &= \left[-\frac{H(2\sqrt{-H}+H)}{(1-\sqrt{-H})^2} \right]^{n-1}, \\ S_{f_{ha}}(3, 2)(H) &= \frac{H(-6\sqrt{-H}-21H+24\sqrt{-H}H+8H^2)}{(-1+3\sqrt{-H}+2H)^2}, \\ S_{f_{ha}}(4, 2)(H) &= \frac{H^3(-28+192\sqrt{-H}+828(-H)^{3/2}+288(-H)^{5/2}+549H-684H^2+48H^3)}{(-1+3\sqrt{-H}+2H)^4}, \\ S_{f_{ha}}(4, 3)(H) &= \frac{2H(6\sqrt{-H}+168(-H)^{3/2}+198(-H)^{5/2}+51H-265H^2+54H^3)}{(-1+6\sqrt{-H}+6(-H)^{3/2}+11H)^2}. \end{aligned}$$

In the Fock basis, the diagonal elements of these operators take the following form:

$$S_{f_{ha}}(n, k)(\alpha_m) = \frac{1}{(m+1)^{2(n-k)}} \sum_{0 \leq p_{n-k} \leq \dots \leq p_1 \leq k} \prod_{i=1}^{n-k} p_i \frac{[2(m+1) - p_i]}{[(m+1) - p_i]^2}, \quad (3.72)$$

Explicitly, for $n \leq 4$, we have:

$$\begin{aligned} S_{f_{ha}}(n, 1, m) &= \left[\frac{2m+1}{m^2(m+1)^2} \right]^{n-1}, \\ S_{f_{ha}}(3, 2, m) &= \frac{6m^3 - 3m^2 + 1}{m^2(m+1)^2(m-1)^2}, \\ S_{f_{ha}}(4, 2, m) &= \frac{28m^6 - 24m^5 + 9m^4 + 8m^3 - 6m^2 + 1}{m^4(1+m)^4(m-1)^4}, \\ S_{f_{ha}}(4, 3, m) &= \frac{2(6m^5 - 21m^4 + 24m^3 - 7m^2 - 2m - 2)}{m^2(1+m)^2(m-1)^2(m-2)^2}. \end{aligned}$$

Let's express it in the following table :

k \ n	1	2	3	4
1	1	$\frac{2m+1}{m^2(m+1)^2}$	$\frac{(2m+1)^2}{m^4(m+1)^4}$	$\frac{(2m+1)^3}{m^6(m+1)^6}$
2		1	$\frac{6m^3-3m^2+1}{m^2(m+1)^2(m-1)^2}$	$\frac{28m^6-24m^5+9m^4+8m^3-6m^2+1}{m^4(m+1)^4(m-1)^4}$
3			1	$\frac{2(6m^5-21m^4+24m^3-7m^2-2m-2)}{m^2(m+1)^2(m-1)^2(m-2)^2}$
4				1

Table 3.1: Generalized Stirling operators $S_{f_{ha}}(n, k, m)$ for the hydrogen atom potential.

Note that $S_{f_{ha}}(n, k, m)$ diverges for $m < k$. In the following list, we give the values of $S(n, k, m)$ for $n \leq 4$ and $k \leq m \leq 7$:

$$\begin{aligned}
S_{f_{ha}}(2, 1, m) &= \left(\frac{3}{4}, \frac{5}{36}, \frac{7}{144}, \frac{9}{400}, \frac{11}{900}, \frac{13}{1764}, \frac{15}{3136} \right), \\
S_{f_{ha}}(3, 1, m) &= \left(\frac{9}{16}, \frac{25}{1269}, \frac{49}{20736}, \frac{81}{160000}, \frac{121}{810000}, \frac{169}{3111696}, \frac{225}{9834496} \right), \\
S_{f_{ha}}(4, 1, m) &= \left(\frac{27}{64}, \frac{125}{46656}, \frac{343}{2985984}, \frac{729}{64000000}, \frac{1131}{729000000}, \frac{2197}{5489031744}, \frac{3375}{30840979456} \right), \\
S_{f_{ha}}(3, 2, m) &= \left(\frac{37}{36}, \frac{136}{576}, \frac{337}{3600}, \frac{679}{14400}, \frac{1189}{44100}, \frac{1912}{112896} \right), \\
S_{f_{ha}}(4, 2, m) &= \left(\frac{403}{432}, \frac{967}{20736}, \frac{92833}{12960000}, \frac{7687}{4320000}, \frac{1132921}{1944810000}, \frac{182179}{796594176} \right), \\
S_{f_{ha}}(4, 3, m) &= \left(\frac{167}{144}, \frac{1091}{900}, \frac{191}{3600}, \frac{3991}{98000}, \frac{29147}{705600} \right).
\end{aligned}$$

3.3.2 Pöschl–Teller Potential

Energy Spectrum for the Pöschl–Teller Potential

The Pöschl–Teller potential is a paradigmatic example of an exactly solvable potential in quantum mechanics. It is used to model symmetric potential wells and plays an important role in molecular physics, quantum optics, and in the study of dynamical symmetries [37, 38].

There are several variants of the Pöschl–Teller potential. We consider here the so-called *hyperbolic* form (or *type I*), defined on the real axis $x \in \mathbb{R}$ by the expression:

$$V(x) = -\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \frac{\nu(\nu-1)}{a^2} \operatorname{sech}^2\left(\frac{x}{a}\right), \quad (3.73)$$

where $\nu > 1$ is a depth parameter of the well, a is a characteristic width scale, and $\operatorname{sech}(x) = 1/\cosh(x)$ [39].

This potential admits a finite number of bound energy levels. Indeed, solving the stationary Schrödinger equation :

$$-\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \frac{d^2\psi}{dx^2} + V(x)\psi(x) = E\psi(x), \quad (3.74)$$

leads to a discrete energy spectrum given by:

$$E_n = -\frac{\hbar^2}{2ma^2}(\nu - 1 - n)^2, \quad \text{where } n = 0, 1, 2, \dots, n_{\max}, \quad (3.75)$$

with $n_{\max} = \lfloor \nu - 1 \rfloor$ [40, 41]. One observes that the number of bound states is thus finite, depending on the depth of the potential via the parameter ν . This property distinguishes the Pöschl–Teller potential from quadratic potentials such as the harmonic oscillator, which have an infinite discrete spectrum.

The wavefunctions associated with the bound energy levels are explicitly written in terms of hypergeometric functions or, more elegantly, in terms of Jacobi polynomials:

$$\psi_n(x) = N_n \operatorname{sech}^{\nu-n}(x/a) P_n^{(\nu-n-1/2, \nu-n-1/2)}\left(\tanh\left(\frac{x}{a}\right)\right), \quad (3.76)$$

where $P_n^{(\alpha, \beta)}(z)$ denotes the Jacobi polynomial and N_n is a normalization constant [42].

The Pöschl–Teller potential is also interesting from an algebraic point of view: it admits a factorization in terms of supersymmetric-type operators, making it a classic example of a *shape-invariant* potential in quantum supersymmetry [43]. This property allows the spectrum to be obtained without explicitly solving the differential equation, via algebraic methods based on commutation relations.

Generalized Heisenberg Algebra

The energy spectrum of the Pöschl–Teller potential is given by:

$$\alpha_n = (n + \nu + 1)^2, \quad (3.77)$$

where ν is an arbitrary constant. Let us determine its characteristic function, denoted by $f_{pl}(\alpha_n) = \alpha_{n+1}$, we have:

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha_{n+1} &= (n + 1 + \nu + 1)^2 \\ &= [(n + \nu + 1)^2 + 2(n + \nu + 1) + 1], \end{aligned} \quad (3.78)$$

which gives:

$$f_{pl}(\alpha_n) = (\alpha_n + 2\sqrt{\alpha_n} + 1) = (\sqrt{\alpha_n} + 1)^2. \quad (3.79)$$

As a function of H , we then have:

$$f_{pl}(H) = \left(\sqrt{H} + 1\right)^2. \quad (3.80)$$

Let us determine the iterated function $f_{pl}^k(H)$ for $n = 2$:

$$f_{pl}^2(H) = \left(\sqrt{f_{pl}(H)} + 1\right)^2 = \left(\sqrt{H} + 2\right)^2, \quad (3.81)$$

by recurrence, we deduce that:

$$f_{pl}^k(H) = \left(\sqrt{H} + k\right)^2. \quad (3.82)$$

Likewise, we can extend this to the inverse characteristic function of $f_{pl}(H)$, we obtain:

$$y_m = \left(\sqrt{f_{pl}(H)} - 1\right)^2, \quad (3.83)$$

which means that $f_{pl}^{-1}(H)$ is given by:

$$f_{pl}^{-1}(H) = \left(\sqrt{H} - 1\right)^2. \quad (3.84)$$

For $k = 2$, we have:

$$f_{pl}^{-2}(H) = \left(\sqrt{f_{pl}^{-1}(H)} - 1\right)^2 = \left(\sqrt{H} - 2\right)^2, \quad (3.85)$$

which gives:

$$f_{pl}^{-k}(H) = \left(\sqrt{H} - k\right)^2. \quad (3.86)$$

Let us now compute the quantum operator $[k]_{f_{pl}}(H)$ associated with the Pöschl–Teller potential. Using (??), we obtain:

$$[k]_{f_{pl}}(H) = k\sqrt{H} + 1. \quad (3.87)$$

For $(k)_{f_{pl}}(H)$, we find:

$$(k)_{f_{pl}}(H) = k[2(n + \nu + 1) - k]. \quad (3.88)$$

Let us now compute the commutation relation associated with the Pöschl–Teller potential. According to (3.16), we write:

$$[a, a^\dagger] = [1]_{f_{pl}}(H) = (\sqrt{H} + 1)^2 - H = 2\sqrt{H} + 1. \quad (3.89)$$

Let us now determine the action of N_f on $|m\rangle$ in the case of the Pöschl–Teller potential. According to (3.38), we write:

$$N_f |m\rangle = [m]_{f_{pl}}(\alpha_0) |m\rangle, \quad (3.90)$$

using (3.13), we write $[m]_{f_{pl}}(\alpha_0)$ as:

$$[m]_{f_{pl}}(\alpha_0) = m\sqrt{\alpha_0} + 1, \quad (3.91)$$

which gives:

$$N_f |m\rangle = (m\sqrt{\alpha_0} + 1) |m\rangle. \quad (3.92)$$

Stirling operators associated with the Pöschl-Teller potential

Let us now calculate the Stirling operators for the Pöschl-Teller potential, using (3.47), we get:

$$S_{f_{pl}}(n, k)(H) = \sum_{0 \leq p_{n-k} \leq \dots \leq p_1 \leq k} \prod_{i=1}^{n-k} [p_i (2\sqrt{H} - p_i)]. \quad (3.93)$$

For the representation in the Fock space, the expression for the Stirling numbers of the second kind becomes:

$$S_{f_{pl}}(n, k)(\alpha_m) = \sum_{0 \leq p_{n-k} \leq \dots \leq p_1 \leq k} \prod_{i=1}^{n-k} [p_i (2(n + \nu + 1) - p_i)]. \quad (3.94)$$

Let us now calculate the Stirling operators for $1 \leq n, k \leq 4$.

$$\begin{aligned} S_{f_{pl}}(2, 1)(\alpha_n) &= 2(n + \nu) + 1, \\ S_{f_{pl}}(3, 1)(\alpha_n) &= [2(n + \nu) + 1]^2, \\ S_{f_{pl}}(4, 1)(\alpha_n) &= [2(n + \nu) + 1]^3, \\ S_{f_{pl}}(3, 2)(\alpha_n) &= 6(n + \nu) + 1, \\ S_{f_{pl}}(4, 2)(\alpha_n) &= [2(n + \nu + 1) - 1][6(n + \nu) + 1] + 4[2(n + \nu + 1) - 2]^2, \\ S_{f_{pl}}(4, 3)(\alpha_n) &= 2[6(n + \nu) - 2]. \end{aligned}$$

We can summarize all this in a table:

k \ n	1	2	3	4
1	1	$2(n + \nu) + 1$	$[2(n + \nu) + 1]^2$	$[2(n + \nu) + 1]^3$
2		1	$6(n + \nu) + 1$	$[2(n + \nu + 1) - 1][6(n + \nu) + 1] + 4[2(n + \nu + 1) - 2]^2$
3			1	$2[6(n + \nu) - 2]$
4				1

Table 3.2: *Generalized Stirling operators $S_{f_{pl}}(n, k, m)$ for the Pöschl-Teller potential.*

Let us calculate the matrix elements for $1 \leq n \leq 7$:

$$S_{f_{pl}}(2, 1)(\alpha_n) = (2\nu + 1, 2\nu + 3, 2\nu + 5, 2\nu + 7, 2\nu + 9, 2\nu + 11, 2\nu + 13),$$

$$S_{f_{pl}}(3, 1)(\alpha_n) = [(2\nu + 1)^2, (2\nu + 3)^2, (2\nu + 5)^2, (2\nu + 7)^2, (2\nu + 9)^2, (2\nu + 11)^2, (2\nu + 13)^2],$$

$$S_{f_{pl}}(4, 1)(\alpha_n) = [(2\nu + 1)^3, (2\nu + 3)^3, (2\nu + 5)^3, (2\nu + 7)^3, (2\nu + 9)^3, (2\nu + 11)^3, (2\nu + 13)^3],$$

$$S_{f_{pl}}(3, 2)(\alpha_n) = (6\nu + 1, 6\nu + 7, 6\nu + 13, 6\nu + 19, 6\nu + 25, 6\nu + 31, 6\nu + 37),$$

$$S_{f_{pl}}(4, 2)(\alpha_n) = [(2\nu + 1)(6\nu + 1) + 4(2\nu)^2, (2\nu + 3)(6\nu + 7) + 4(2\nu + 2)^2, \dots],$$

$$S_{f_{pl}}(4, 3)(\alpha_n) = (12\nu - 4, 12\nu + 8, 12\nu + 20, 12\nu + 32, 12\nu + 44, 12\nu + 56, 12\nu + 68).$$

Remark:

In the case where $\nu \rightarrow 0$, one recovers the results of the infinite square well potential.

k \ n	1	2	3	4
1	1	$2(n + \nu) + 1$	$(2n + 1)^2$	$(2n + 1)^3$
2		1	$6n + 1$	$1 + 8n + 28n^2$
3			1	$2(6n - 2)$
4				1

Table 3.3: *Generalized Stirling operators $S_{f_{pl}}(n, k, m)$ for the infinite square well potential*

The Pöschl–Teller potential is an attractive finite-depth potential, defined by (3.73), where the parameter $\nu > 0$ controls the depth of the well. This potential is negative at the center ($x = 0$) and tends to zero as $x \rightarrow \pm\infty$. It always remains finite, which implies that only a finite number of bound states (i.e. with $E_n < 0$) can exist. The maximum number of bound levels is given by:

$$n_{\max} = \lfloor \nu \rfloor. \quad (3.95)$$

As ν increases, the well becomes deeper, allowing more bound quantum states to exist. In the limit $\nu \rightarrow \infty$, the potential becomes extremely deep and narrow, and the number of bound states tends to infinity. One then reaches an asymptotic situation equivalent to that of the infinite square well, defined by:

$$V(x) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } 0 < x < L, \\ +\infty & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (3.96)$$

In this case, the particle is perfectly confined in the region $[0, L]$, and an infinite number of discrete energy levels are obtained. Thus, by letting ν tend to infinity, one goes from a model with a finite discrete spectrum (Pöschl–Teller) to a model with an infinite discrete spectrum (infinite square well).

Conclusion

In this thesis, we have explored a deep and rich connection between combinatorial mathematics and quantum physics, particularly through the study of Stirling numbers and their role in the normal and anti-normal ordering of quantum operators. Beginning with the theoretical foundations of the quantum harmonic oscillator and coherent states, we highlighted how these concepts give rise to algebraic structures governed by creation and annihilation operators, and how such structures naturally lead to combinatorial expressions involving Stirling numbers.

The second part of this work focused on a detailed analysis of classical and generalized Stirling numbers. We examined their recurrence relations, generating functions, and their appearance in the algebraic manipulation of operator products. We paid particular attention to q -deformations, which enrich the structure of the Heisenberg algebra and reveal a broader landscape of operator behavior in quantum systems.

In the final chapter, we introduced generalized Stirling operators associated with specific quantum potentials, such as the hydrogen atom and the Pöschl–Teller potential. These constructions allowed us to establish a bridge between discrete combinatorial sequences and continuous quantum systems, offering an algebraic insight into their spectral properties and symmetries.

Perspectives: Beyond the results presented here, several promising research directions emerge:

- The formalism developed in this thesis can be naturally extended to quantum systems with symmetries described by quantum groups or q -deformed Lie algebras. In particular, the link between q -Stirling numbers and the representation theory of quantum groups deserves further exploration.
- Another exciting direction is the study of Hopf algebras and their duality structures, which provide a powerful framework for understanding algebraic deformations. Stirling operators could be interpreted as structural coefficients in these algebras.
- In the context of quantum information theory, the combinatorics underlying operator ordering could be applied to analyze entanglement structures and resource

states, especially in systems modeled by non-classical algebras.

- Finally, from a purely mathematical standpoint, investigating non-integer or interpolated Stirling numbers in operator settings may uncover new connections between discrete mathematics, functional analysis, and quantum field theory.

In conclusion, the generalizations of Stirling numbers offer not only elegant mathematical structures but also powerful tools for analyzing complex physical systems. This interplay between combinatorics and quantum theory continues to be a fertile ground for theoretical and applied research.

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